

BRIGHT SPACE

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Deliverable D8.1: Report on the provision of a set of promising technologies relevant to Safe and Just Operating Space

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DATE OF APPROVAL:	26.04.2024
APPROVED BY PROJECT COORDINATOR:	Marc Müller (WR)
DATE OF APPROVAL:	30.04.2024
CALL	Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
WORK PROGRAMME Topic ID	EU agriculture within a safe and just operating space and planetary boundaries HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-12
PROJECT WEB SITE:	https://brightspace-project.eu/

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History of changes

Version	Publication date	Changes	Who
0.1	15.03.2024	Draft Version	Lukáš Čechura
0.2	10.04.2024	Internal Review	Hugo Storm
1.1	26.04.2024	Consolidation/Approval	Lukáš Čechura
1.2	30.04.2024	Approval	Marc Müller

Citation:

Ahado, S., Žáková Kroupová, Z., Čechura, L., Pokorný, O., Curtiss, J., Ratinger, T., (2024). Deliverable D8.1 (D18) Report on the provision of a set of promising technologies relevant to Safe and Just Operating Space. BrightSpace Horizon Europe project GA Nr. 101060075.

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ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPS	Global Positioning System
IoT	Internet of Things
SJOS	Safe and Just Operating Space
AI	Artificial Intelligence
TC	Technology Centre Prague
WoS	Web of Science
WP8	Work Package 8

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Report on the Provision of a set of Promising Technologies Relevant to Safe and Just Space Operating Space (SJOS) is the first report of Work Package 8 (WP8) of the BrightSpace research project. One of the aims of the project is to identify strategies for current agri-food systems to strengthen and adopt production and processing practices that would lead to climate neutrality and eliminate the negative environmental and social impacts, as targeted by the European Green Deal. The objectives of the European Green Deal are closely linked to the transformation of the agri-food sector, a transformation that depends critically on the successful adoption of emerging technologies that contribute to operating within the Safe and Just Operating Space. Given the importance of sustainable technological innovation and adoption, the core objective of this study is to identify key emerging technologies and innovations in agricultural production and food processing and their alignment with the SJOS. In line with this objective, this report presents the results of an extensive scan of emerging technologies, their systematization, and a literature review mapping the existing empirical evidence on their impact on the SJOS.

The study employs a systemic methodological approach, combining artificial intelligence-based technology scans, a systematic literature, and qualitative comparative analyses. It leverages the TC technology scan tool to identify relevant technologies and clusters them into meaningful categories using the topic modeling tool (Latent Dirichlet Allocation application). A systematic review of the literature further elucidates the implications of identified technologies for the SJOS, enriching the study with existing empirical findings and expert insights.

The technology scan identified 62 key emerging technologies for agriculture and food processing, which were categorized and assigned to six clusters. The literature review helped to extract existing empirical evidence on 13 technologies that already show significant promise in terms of their contribution to advancing the sector towards the SJOS. Among the promising technologies in the Decision Tools cluster, artificial intelligence (AI), decision support systems, and big data (including the Internet of Things) were found to be of high scientific interest. Blockchain is also emerging as a frontrunner, demonstrating profound potential to enhance food security and economic resilience in the agri-food sector. Genome editing, biofortification, nitrogen-fixing bacteria, and in vitro culture within Gene Change technologies were also found to be promising in terms of their impact on sustainability. For the Robotic Agriculture cluster, the literature points to a future potential mainly in farm automation. Within the Integrative technology cluster, the academic focus is on regenerative agriculture. Among the technologies in the Transparent Food cluster, hyperspectral imaging stands out as the technology that has demonstrated a significant contribution to SJOS so far. In the Rural-Urban Technology cluster, vertical farming emerges as the only technology with promising prospects. The results underline the promising role of technological progress in achieving the SJOS and the ambitious strategic goals of the EU.

This deliverable forms the basis for the subsequent research within WP8 (Task 8.1). In the next research steps, AI and the literature-based identification of promising technologies will be complemented by experts' assessment. With the help of expert panels, the promising technologies will be evaluated in terms of their technological parameters as well their scalability and ability to fill critical SJOS gaps and drive transformative change.

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Union's commitment to the European Green Deal is intricately linked to the transformation of the agri-food sector, a transformation that hinges on the effective integration of emerging technologies. These technologies, ranging from precision agriculture and robotics to data analytics, are central to moving the sector toward the Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS), a framework designed to assess whether agricultural practices are environmentally sustainable, economically viable, and socially equitable.

Emerging technologies in agriculture are those new and rapidly evolving technological innovations that are still in the nascent stages of adoption but demonstrate significant potential to transform food production and processing (Rotolo et al., 2015). They are characterized by their novel applications, potential to enhance productivity and sustainability, and their role in addressing the pressing challenges of food security and climate change (Geels, 2022). These broad implications for agricultural producers and consumers render them key drivers for maintaining competitive European agriculture in a global world. Promising technologies within the domain of emerging technologies are defined as those that not only align with the innovative edge of emerging technologies but also exhibit a direct link to the SJOS indicators, offering solutions that are likely to contribute positively to the agri-food sector's sustainability, resilience and social justice.

In alignment with the objectives of the BrightSpace project, this first WP8 deliverable identifies and explores the emerging technologies with an eye towards their contribution to a sustainable agricultural paradigm, one that reduces the environmental footprint of food production, enhances biodiversity, optimizes resource use, and supports the well-being of consumers and producers alike. This exploration is framed within a systematic approach that assesses the technological landscape, identifies key innovations, evaluates their alignment with the SJOS. This exploratory analysis sets the stage for the follow-up qualitative (expert-based) assessment of the promising technologies' SJOS potentials and ultimately for providing a roadmap for their effective integration into the EU's agri-food sector.

Beginning with the description of the applied methods in the next chapter (Chapter 2), this deliverable unfolds through a structured analysis that commences with the detection and clustering of emerging technologies (Section 3.1). This analysis is underpinned by a robust methodological approach that combines machine learning, topic modeling, and expert assessment. It progresses to a systematic literature review of the empirical evidence on the environmental and socio-economic impacts of these technologies, offering insights into the preliminary assessment of their potential to foster a transition towards the SJOS (Section 3.2). The document then delves into the description and qualitative assessment of the technologies identified in Section 3.2 and their (expected) impact on the SJOS (Section 3.3). The manuscript concludes with Chapter 4. It provides a synthesis of the findings and an outline of the planned qualitative research that will allow a deeper assessment of the identified technologies in terms of their potential contribution to achieving the strategic objectives for the advancement of the EU agricultural sector within the framework of the SJOS.

2. METHODS

The methodologies applied in the first task of WP8 aim to systematically scan and identify emerging technologies that may be promising in terms of their capacity to navigate the agri-food sector towards the SJOS. This chapter outlines the adopted methodologies, which represent approaches for (i) AI-scanning, (ii) clustering of emerging technologies, and (iii) systematic literature review and description of the technologies that have already demonstrated their impact on the SJOS. These methodological steps are the precursors to the subsequent systematic technology and policy assessment by expert panels.

2.1. Scan and Identification of Emerging Technologies Detection

The volume of publicly available information sources devoted to describing technological innovations and emerging technologies has grown steadily in recent years. We scanned and evaluated large textual data from numerous sources to ensure accurate and comprehensive identification of emerging technologies relevant to the agri-food sector. The Technology Centre Prague (TC) has its own analytical tool that allows TO manage and analyze such data. The software is based on Python programming language libraries, which are publicly available for free use for the analysis of large text data, natural language and large language models. It thus enables detailed analysis of complex information contained in the analyzed texts. This software system has been adapted to the needs of the project using machine learning and trained to collect appropriate structured and unstructured data on technological trends and innovations related to the thematic scope of the BrightSpace project.

The scanning process also considered the relevance of the technological advancements to the SJOS. To identify key emerging technologies with the potential to improve the performance of the agri-food sector in terms of the values presented by the SJOS, it was necessary to define keywords that adequately represent the individual SJOS domains as detailed in WP1. In most cases, English keywords and phrases were searched for in the titles and abstracts of the following documents and databases that TC has subscribed to:

- Project materials for the relevant calls of the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe framework programs (Common Research Data Warehouse database),
- Scientific publications (Clarivate Analysis Web of Science database),
- European Patent Office (PATSTAT) patent applications (EPO Worldwide Patent Statistical Database).

The keywords were designed to ensure that the records found in the databases cover the maximum part of the issue and contain a minimum number of "fake" records that are not related to the issue. For this reason, the selected keywords were verified by the ChatGPT_4 chatbot, and finally the keywords were eventually expertly modified according to the AI results.

The primary set of keywords was used to search for relevant texts in information sources. The Web of Science (WoS) database was used for scanning emerging technologies in modern agriculture. The analytical tool was connected to the available information sources via Application Programming Interface (API) and automatically collected and analyzed documents according to the input criteria (keywords and their combinations). Keywords are an essential part of any document, as they provide a concise representation of the document's content. At the same time, they enable us to locate the article in the information system, or to categorize the document into appropriate thematic groups. Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools were used to analyze the text data, where individual texts were converted into a dataset based on the frequency of individual words. With the help of lemmatization, all words in the dataset were converted into their basic form. Subsequently, the most

common words (prepositions, conjunctions, pronouns, etc.) were removed so that these words would not affect the results relevant to the contextual extraction of new information.

To extract keywords from the abstracts, it was necessary to convert the text from the created corpus into a format that could be interpreted by machine learning algorithms. Text tokenization and vectorization were used for this purpose. Tokenization allows continuous to be converted into a list of words. Vectorization then converts the resulting word list into an array of integers. The order of the words was ignored and their frequency in the corpus was considered. The vectorization further refined the resulting matrix, making it possible to identify context-specific words from the entire corpus. The Term Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency method is used for the vectorization, which made it possible to eliminate words that appear many times in the document and, on the contrary, to highlight words that are essential and unique to a particular document, distinguishing it from the rest of the corpus. The scan was performed between 24-30 April 2023 and resulted in an extensive list of emerging technologies developed for or with potential implementation in the agri-food sector.

2.2. Technology Clustering

The processed texts were subsequently clustered according to their content. To identify technology groups, topic clustering tools were applied that use words that are common in the group's documents. Clusters of texts are found by searching for groups of objects that are more similar to each other than to members of other groups. Therefore, the goal of clustering analysis is to distinguish a set of groups in which the similarity with other clusters is minimal and the internal similarity of documents is maximum.

The resulting technology clusters were further analyzed using advanced machine learning techniques, which made it possible to identify patterns and trends in the contained texts. Specifically, the topic modeling tool (Latent Dirichlet Allocation application) was used to identify hidden thematic structures in the text. Subsequently, the identified topics were subjected to context mapping, which allowed us to observe how the meaning and context of the topics change over time and helped to reveal new trends and relationships between topics in the text data. This method provides a comprehensive insight into the relationships of groups of words that occur together in the context of a selected keyword in different time periods and allows to define the basis for detecting anomalies in text data. Anomaly detection allows for identification of topics that are unique within a given cluster and that distinguishes it from others. This makes it possible to define signals of future technologies relevant to the overall research focus.

The technology clusters (see *Table A1. Scan of Emerging Technologies* in the Appendix) identified by means of the advanced machine learning techniques were then expertly assessed in terms of functionality and scope of application. The final in-house expert assessment allowed technologies with the most similar characteristics to be grouped into homogeneous clusters representing emerging technologies' typology.

2.3. Literature Review on impact of Emerging Technologies

A comprehensive literature review was conducted as the initial step in the of the potential of the emerging technologies to facilitate the transition of the agri-food sector towards the SJOS The aim of the review was to examine existing empirical evidence and/or scientific discourse pertaining to their (anticipated) environmental and socio-economic impacts. Specifically, the review examined six clusters of emerging technologies to the 12 thematic areas of the SJOS relevant to the EU agricultural system identified in WP1. These are: *climate change, chemical pollution, aerosol loading, biodiversity, nutrient flow, land and water use, nutritional security, farm resilience, economy, social equity, and health.*

In terms of methodology, the WoS database was used as the primary source. The subject headings (keywords) for each technology cluster were derived from the principal technologies within each

cluster. The keywords for thematic areas were based on an understanding of the SJOS dimensions and control variables as specified in pioneering papers by Steffen et al. (2015), Raworth (2012) and Rockström et al. (2009). The concatenated keywords that form the search queries can be found in Table A3 in the Appendix.

From the search output, only fully published and English language studies were considered and included in the search results. From these, relevant studies were screened and selected. This procedure was performed in two steps: 1) titles, abstracts, and keywords were examined to assess their thematic match; 2) relevant studies were selected based on a qualified assessment of the information of interest identified in the full text. The search was conducted between January 19 and February 6, 2024.

The retrieved publications were then subjected to an in-depth qualitative content analysis with regard to the technologies' detected contributions to the individual dimensions of the SJOS. Aspects considered in the analysis include the extent of the impact found in the scientific literature and the record frequency.

It is important to recognize that the literature review can predominantly identify technologies that have been either broadly tested or are already in use, reflecting a higher degree of technological readiness. The publication record frequency may also reflect the scope of technology implementation, which could be influenced by the available knowledge, information systems, and existing regulatory frameworks. Additionally, the choice of keywords used in the literature search could significantly affect the results obtained. On the other hand, the volume of scientific publications on a particular technology mirrors the scientific community's interest and may suggest the technology's promising benefits to the agri-food sector.

In the next phases of Task 8.1, expert panels will critically assess and pinpoint the most promising emerging technologies. These technologies will be those that exhibit the highest potential based on their contributions to the Safe and Just Operating Space (SJOS), scalability, and other crucial impact indicators that align with the goals of the EU Green Deal.

3. RESULTS

This section presents the results of the technology scan and clustering, which yielded a typology of the core emerging technologies for the agri-food sector. It also documents the implications of emerging technologies and their characteristics and impact for Safe and Just Operating Space. The section concludes with a discussion of the most promising technologies with high scalability and adoption by the scientific community.

3.1. Identification and Typology of Emerging Technologies

The AI-based technology scan identified a total of 110 emerging technologies relevant to the agri-food sector. The technologies were expertly assessed in terms of functionality, scope of application and impact. Technologies with similar characteristics were merged and the resulting file contains 62 technologies. Six clusters mapped the identified technologies: decision-making tools, gene change, integrative technology, robotic farmers, rural-urban and transparent food technologies.

Technologies in agriculture have taken the shape of biological advances and technical advances (also includes clean technology). In this paper, we classified the technologies in agriculture into six clusters (see Table 1). The first cluster is decision tool technology and its uses sensor networks that collect climatic, environmental, geographical, and social data for application in agriculture. The second cluster of technology is gene change. This technology encompasses altering the gene of organisms and transforming them into new products. The third group of technologies is integrative technology. This

technology aims to decentralize the existing food system, amplifying access to nutritious food and knowledge. The fourth category of technology is the robot farmer. This technology comprises agriculture 3.0 and 4.0, which mainly uses sensors and robots (automation) for agricultural production. The fifth cluster is urban-rural technology and is more prominent in the city and countryside. This technology changes the relationships between those producers and consumers. The last cluster of technology is transparency food, which uses transparent solutions and data platforms to create new standards for quality, safety, and authenticity of agricultural food chains. The classified technology clusters are described in more detail below.

Decision Tools

The technology in the Decision Tools cluster is a tool for changing the approach to agricultural management, which uses the power of advanced technologies to optimize decision-making processes and improve the overall efficiency of agricultural production. The cluster encompasses a diverse range of technologies, from sensor networks and artificial intelligence to digital twins and blockchain, all aimed at providing farmers with a high level of quality data and information for decision-making.

A feature of the technologies in this cluster is the integration of software and hardware systems for collecting and analyzing operational and operational data from sensor networks. With data analytics and predictive modeling tools, these systems can provide farmers with valuable insights and recommendations to optimize inputs, irrigation practices, and crop selection, ultimately leading to improved yields and profitability.

In addition, the inclusion of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and blockchain have the potential to further improve the capabilities of decision-making tools in agriculture. AI algorithms can analyze complex datasets and create predictive models, allowing farmers to anticipate challenges and optimize management strategies. Blockchain technology offers secure and transparent data storage and sharing, ensuring the integrity and traceability of agricultural data throughout the supply chain.

Overall, the Farming Decision Tools cluster represents technologies with great potential for transformation to data-driven precision agriculture. The application of sensor network and information technology technologies will enable farmers to make informed decisions that enhance environmental sustainability, optimize resource use, and create more harmonious and balanced ecosystems.

Gene change

A profound shift is underway in gene-altering technologies that will enable changes in our approach to agriculture and environmental sustainability. These advances represent a departure from traditional methods relying on pesticides, fertilizers, and antibiotics, which have contributed to widespread environmental degradation.

The cluster incorporates innovative technologies that harness the power of genetic manipulation to create solutions that are more sustainable, efficient, and environmentally friendly. From algae-based meal substitutes to in vitro meat production, scientists are reshaping food production systems from the ground up, harnessing the potential of genetic modification to create nutritious, environmentally sustainable alternatives to conventional agriculture. Other technologies, such as bacteriophages, offer new approaches to combat antibiotic resistance in livestock, while biofortification will make it possible to address nutritional deficiencies in crops. These and other technologies not only offer solutions to pressing problems in agriculture and food security, but also have the potential for veterinary advances, especially in the field of livestock reproduction.

Overall, the cluster of gene-altering technologies represents the potential to change the approach to solving large agricultural challenges. By using genetic manipulation technologies, food production can be made more sustainable, antibiotics will be used sparingly, and human health and the environment

will be prioritized. As these technologies continue to evolve, they hold promise to transform industries and shape a more resilient and sustainable future for future generations.

Integrative Technologies

The cluster, titled integrative technologies, contains innovations that represent a paradigm shift in agricultural production towards collaborative, decentralized networks that will enable expanded access to agricultural products.

These innovations foster dynamic relationships and cooperation between individuals, communities, and institutions throughout the food system. Through digital platforms, data sharing, and communication technologies, stakeholders are empowered to pool resources, expertise, and best practices to create resilient and responsive food networks that prioritize global health and equity. The primary catalyst for this development is the proliferation of new technologies that facilitate seamless connectivity and collaboration across the entire food value chain. The producer-processor-consumer networks can increasingly rely on advanced data analytics and AI algorithms that play a key role in optimizing production, distribution, and consumption processes, ensuring efficient resource allocation and minimizing waste. Additionally, emerging technologies such as blockchain offer transparent and traceable supply chains, fostering trust and accountability between stakeholder groups. These innovative models and tools that support decentralized food production and cooperation in agricultural production have the potential to strengthen reliable and responsible food systems.

Although identified as emerging technologies through the applied methodology, they are not technologies per se. Rather, they represent collaborative social innovations or collaborative supply chain networks, the development of which can be significantly facilitated by the emerging digital technologies as these can support their complex governance. For this reason, these collaborative governance models that are emerging in the agri-food sector will be analyzed in a greater depth among governance innovations in the next deliverable of WP8.

The AI-based clustering approach also allocated some sustainable farming practices to the integrative technology cluster, specifically, regenerative agriculture. These farming approaches, which are not standalone technologies enable year-round production in both urban and rural settings, minimize water and land use, ensure soil carbon maintenance and restore ecosystems, thereby contribute to the long-term resilience and sustainability of food systems. Farming practices, such as regenerative agriculture, have also a long history, reaching back to the 1980s and as such cannot be considered "emerging". It is probable that these practices were identified by the scan due to their social and environmental contribution and their notable potential for implementing technological innovations.

Robot Farmers

The cluster contains technologies that drive transformational changes in agricultural practices and that use state-of-the-art robotic technologies to enhance the sustainability and efficiency of agricultural production. Technology will enable agricultural production towards automation, efficiency, and accuracy of farming practices to address key challenges such as potential labor shortages, rising costs, and environmental sustainability.

The cluster contains several robotic technologies used to optimize various aspects of agricultural activities. Sophisticated sensor technologies enable precise monitoring and control of agricultural operations, from soil health and moisture levels to crop growth and pest infestations. At the same time, they will provide farmers with real-time data and insights, sensors and robots enabling them to make informed decisions that optimize resource use and minimize environmental impact, improving crop yields and profitability.

In addition, the proliferation of farm robots has the potential to exponentially increase food production while reducing contamination and waste. Robots equipped with advanced harvesting and sorting

capabilities can streamline the production process, ensuring that only the highest quality product reaches consumers.

Overall, the application of technology in this cluster represents a paradigm shift in farming practices, ushering in a new era of smart, efficient, and sustainable agriculture. By harnessing the power of robotic technology, farmers can overcome traditional barriers to productivity and profitability while reducing their environmental footprint and contributing to global food security.

Urban-Rural

The technologies included in the Urban-Rural cluster will enable the development of a dynamic fusion of urban and rural landscapes and their use for agricultural production. Technology will make it possible to change traditional notions of food production, consumption, and sustainability, and will gradually make it possible to bridge the gap between urban centers and rural areas. The technologies in this cluster contribute primarily to the sustainability and efficiency of food production, shortening its production chain, which favors proximity between producers and consumers. This process is made possible by innovative approaches to food production, distribution and consumption, which support the technologies contained in the cluster.

By leveraging advanced techniques such as 3D printing, automated home farming, and vertical farming, communities can grow fresh, nutritious food in a variety of settings, from dense urban neighborhood to remote rural areas. The Farm-in-a-box concept further reinforces this vision of self-sufficiency and resilience, offering off-grid farming solutions that can be deployed in a variety of settings, including urban rooftops and even shipping containers. This decentralized approach to agriculture not only reduces reliance on traditional farming practices but also encourages community and individual involvement in the production of their own food.

Overall, the Urban-Rural cluster represents a holistic approach to food systems transformation, where technological innovation, sustainability, and community resilience converge to create a fairer, more efficient, and greener future for food production and consumption.

Transparent Food

The cluster contains mostly disruptive digital technologies that have a high potential to enable the further development of fair agricultural production, significantly transform food value chains, contribute to more productive, resilient and transparent food systems. At the same time, technologies can support changes in today's food industry and can contribute to better integration of smallholder farmers into production and value chains through a transparent, more efficient and inclusive approach to the agricultural market. This potential is offered by integrated technologies, especially as they can gradually address the reduction of information asymmetries and transaction costs.

From the point of view of the user of agricultural products, the technologies contained in the cluster represent a groundbreaking approach to revolutionizing our understanding of food production, distribution and consumption. Technology can contribute to greater transparency in terms of food production source and openness of production processes in the food industry. As a result, these technologies can allow consumers to have an unprecedented level of transparency and control over what they eat. Thus, the technologies of the Transparent Food cluster are driving a new era of transparency, accountability, and sustainability in the global food system. By providing consumers with knowledge and insight, this initiative has the potential to transform the way we produce, distribute, and consume food, promoting a healthier and fairer future for all.

Table 1. Typology of Emerging Technologies for the Agri-food Sector

Clusters	Technology	Description
Decision Tools	Context-aware biology open Tool	A temperature sensor technology that provides farmers on-farm real-time feedback for better decision-making
	Decision support system	Provides insight into input application and guides farmers in varying treatment
	In-Silico farming	A technology that collects data from crops and create mathematical models to simulate yields
	Predictive weather model	Aggregates weather data and provides forecasting for farmers in areas of planting and harvesting decisions
	Artificial intelligence (AI)	Provides insights, predictive forecasts, chatbots, anomaly/disease recognition, and gene selection recommendations to farmers
	Digital twins	A technology that collects data from the soil and analyzes past patterns to simulate future behavior
	Machine vision	Utilizes computer vision and image recognition analyze crop condition, weed identification, and harvesting
	Big data and analytics	A technology that transforms farm data into actionable insights enabling farmers to identify patterns and relationships in the farm
	Block chain	Technology that tracks plant information, regulate food quality, and monitor supply chain
	Cloud competing	A technology that enables efficient management of technology solutions, data, and predictive intelligence models
Gene Change	Algae based meal replacement	Fast-growing plant organisms that can be used as meal replacements with controlled calories and nutrients
	Bacteriophages	A non-antibiotic bacterial virus used to combat common infections like mastitis, preserving drug efficacy/promoting animal health.
	Biofortification	Breeding crops to enhance their nutritional value, either through selective breeding or genetic engineering
	Computer-assisted transgenesis	Precision robotics and computer vision algorithms used to expedite the production of transgenic organisms
	Cyborg sperm	A hybrid micromotor with microhelices guides sperm's tail towards an egg, using magnetic fields. This technology accelerates livestock and human reproduction
	De-extinction	Creating extinct species or breeding populations, with cloning
	Endophytic plant protection	Plant microbes as alternative to synthetic pesticides to improve crop performance
	Gene drive	A technology that increases the chance of a gene being passed to offspring, could be used to eradicate plagues and weeds
	Genome editing (CRISPR)	A genetic engineering technique that improves food safety, extend shelf life, and develop new products with desirable traits
	In-vitro meat	Lab-grown animal protein with minimal effects on the environment during it production
	Nitrogen fixing bacteria	Involves coating seeds with bacteria to aid plants in reclaiming nitrogen from atmosphere
	Optimized photosynthesis	Uses the enzyme Rubisco to convert carbon dioxide into sugar for plants
	Porous nanozeolite	These are zeolites, aluminosilicate variations and are used in the industry sector as adsorbents and catalysts
	RNA interference spray	A biotechnology that reverses the effects on organisms by blocking specific genes using spray-on technology
	Mini chromosome technology	A technology that enhances plant traits without altering genes, making plants drought-tolerant or pest-resistant
Upgrading photosynthesis	Upgrading genetically modified crops by making plants to absorb excess energy	
Transgenic organism	Altering the genome of an organism with a DNA of a different traits	
Integrative technology	Agricultural linguistics model	Digitized global agriculture models that can be created using environmental, atmospheric, and diagnostic sensor data
	Co-farming	Practice that involves utilizing online sharing platforms like Airbnb to rent or share farm machinery
	Farm-to-consumer network	Practice that enables direct food access through mobile apps, online ordering, and wholesale platforms
	Open phenome library	A database that stores and links genetic information, environmental inputs, and species-specific outputs
	Predictive food insecurity warning	A system that uses real-time data combination to create short- and mid-term warning signals of approaching food insecurity
	RFID	Tags crops and animals with unique ID numbers, improves waste management, and increases supply chain transparency
	Regenerative agriculture	Farming practice that rebuilds soil organic matter and restores biodiversity, replacing harmful chemicals and pesticides

Table 1. Typology of Emerging Technologies for the Agri-food Sector (continued)

Cluster	Technology	Description
Robot Farmers	Animal-robot interaction	Intelligent systems that allow owners to remotely interact and care for their livestock without the need for physical presence
	Atmospheric water harvesting	Using micro-netting to harvest water from abundant air moisture
	Autonomous agriculture vehicle	Autonomous self-propelled vehicles, using video cameras, radar, accelerometers, LIDAR system, and software, perform agricultural activities and transportation without a driver
	Bio-electricity farm	It uses soil bacteria in plants break down organic matter, releasing electrons for electricity.
	Pollinating robot bee	Robots mimic animal and insect behavior, like pollination by honeybees, to perform various functions, especially in the face of declining honeybee health, which is crucial for food and beverage production
	Bio-refinery	Bio-refineries convert biomass into bioproducts, reducing waste and improving efficiency
	Freight drone	This technology uses drones to apply pesticides, potentially opening new farming areas in mountainous regions
	Laser scarecrows	Using green laser light to scare birds from damaging crops
	Milk bot	Laser-enabled transponders on cows' necks, scan and map their underbellies, track milking speed, quality, frequency, daily steps
	Robot farm	Are plant factories, powered by programmed machines and sensors, that automate seed and provides care to the crops
	Robotic farm labor	These techs are AI advancements that mimic robots to replace human labor in agriculture, including pruning, weeding, spraying, and monitoring
	Robot-monitored agric. system	Sensor-controlled gadgets monitoring crop nutrients, water-stress, disease, insect infestations, and plant health
	Farm automation	Combines agricultural machinery, computer systems, electronics, and data management to improve field operations
Rural-Urban	3D printed food	Uses macronutrients such as starch, protein and fat, recipes to make ready-to-eat food with appealing shapes and textures
	Automated home farming	Robotic farming that uses computer-controlled actuators to automate tasks like seeding, watering, fertilizing, and weed removal
	Farm-in-a-box	Used as off-grid farming, including cargo containers, greenhouse grow operations, hydroponics, and indoor agriculture
	Floating farm barge	The technology involves using hydroponics, aquaculture, or greenhouse methods, could provide a new food cultivation method in regions with limited land, soil, or water access
	Seaweed forest	Algal forests replace fossil fuels, reduce carbon dioxide emissions, provide food, aid fisheries recovery and marine life diversity
	Super water absorbing material	The use of upsalite a porous magnesium carbonate to absorb large amounts of liquid, improve food storage in agriculture
	Terraforming desert	Transforming desert into viable habitats or new farmland through solar power and modern agriculture
	Vertical farming	Utilizing blue and red LED lighting for organic, pesticide-free food growth in automated indoor environments
Transparent food	Agro-waste biodegradable coating	Uses agricultural byproducts and waste, like orange peels, as biodegradable coatings
	Augmented reality information transfer	Offers a more interactive and informative learning environment, simplifying tasks like agriculture or gardening maintenance
	DNA fingerprinting food	DNA fingerprinting used as a forensic tool to trace the origin of plant and animal materials
	Food computer	A robotic-controlled environment for programming plants to yield various phenotypic expressions, allowing for standardized agricultural experiments
	Hyperspectral imaging	A technology that is used for surveillance, food quality control, and Earth imaging
	Miniature mass spectrometry	Chemical analysis using vaporization, ionization, and spectral analysis
	Food-NanoTag Technology	The technology uses nano barcodes, luminous proteins, and nano-sensors to monitor and tag food items, detecting contamination, and improving supply chain efficiency

3.2. Impact of Emerging Technologies on SJOS

The results of the literature review on the scientifically documented contributions of emerging technologies to the SJOS are presented in the following two subsections. Section 3.2.1 presents the scientific record statistics, while Section 3.2.2 discusses the specific technological impacts within each thematic area of the SJOS.

3.2.1. Frequency of scientific records for SJOS domains

The review of the extent of knowledge on the impact of emerging technologies on the SJOS thematic dimensions encompassed a comprehensive examination of the scientific literature indexed in the WoS, with a focus on 62 technologies that were identified and selected in the previous step of the analysis. It is important to note that the literature review can predominantly identify studies on technologies that have been either broadly tested or are already in use. This reflects a higher degree of technological readiness. The publication numbers may also reflect the scope of technology implementation, which could be influenced by the available knowledge, information systems, and existing regulatory frameworks. Additionally, the choice of keywords used in the literature search could significantly affect the results obtained. Conversely, the volume of scientific publications on a particular technology mirrors the scientific community's interest and may suggest the technology's promising benefits to the agri-food sector.

Table 2 presents the number of relevant WoS records identified for the 12 SJOS thematic areas. Figure 1 offers a visual presentation of the frequency of the SJOS domains, as analyzed in relation to the technologies in the six technology clusters. This highlights the areas of significant academic focus and potential impact of these technologies on the agri-food sector. Notably, Nutritional Security emerges as a prominent area of study, particularly within the Decision Tools and Gene Change technology clusters, indicating a significant research emphasis on how these technologies can enhance food quality and security. This focus reflects the critical role of agritech in addressing global challenges related to nutrition and food availability. There is also a noticeable amount of research related to Climate Change, particularly in the Decision Tools cluster, indicating a significant interest in how these technologies can address climate-related challenges in agriculture. While there are some studies in the Biodiversity dimension, the numbers are relatively lower compared to Nutritional Security and Climate Change. This suggests a lesser but still notable focus on how technologies impact agricultural biodiversity. The Health (Nutritional Security) indicator also sees a fair number of studies, especially in the technology clusters Decision Tools and Gene Change, indicating interest in how technologies can influence health outcomes related to agriculture. Chemical Pollution and Water Use SJOS domains show a relatively low number of studies, indicating a surprisingly moderate empirical evidence or research interest in how technologies can mitigate chemical pollution and optimize water use in agriculture. Surprisingly, the literature review found a limited number of scientific papers for the SJOS domains of Economy and Resilience, which may require further attention. The SJOS areas of Land Use, Aerosol Loading, and Social Equity show so far minimal research activity, highlighting potential gaps in the current research landscape and areas that may benefit from increased attention. These search and review results organized around the SJOS thematic areas are discussed in more detail in the following sections.

Table 2. Number of Search Results and Relevant Studies on the SJOS Impact of Emerging Technologies

Technology Cluster/SJOS Indicator		Bio-diversity	Climate change	Nutrient flow	Land use	Water use	Chemical Pollution	Aerosol loading	Nutritional Security	Health	Social equity	Economy	Resilience
Decision Tools	Artificial intelligence	0	16(3)	4 (1)	0	1 (1)	8 (1)	0	65 (14)	19 (0)	0	3 (1)	5 (1)
	Decision support system	4 (1)	30 (0)	22 (8)	4 (1)	2 (1)	15 (2)	3 (1)	39 (5)	7 (0)	0	9 (0)	5 (0)
	Digital twins	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3 (0)	1 (0)	0	0	0
	Big data	6(0)	23 (5)	7 (1)	1 (0)	2 (1)	5 (0)	0	77 (8)	12 (0)	0	10 (2)	13 (1)
	Blockchain	0	3 (1)	1 (0)	0	0	2 (0)	0	33 (3)	1 (0)	0	2 (2)	3 (0)
Gene Change	Bacteriophage	0	0	0	0	1 (1)	1 (1)	0	4 (0)	2 (1)	0	0	0
	Biofortification	8 (1)	0	7 (4)	0	0	4 (1)	0	52 (6)	24 (6)	0	8 (0)	1 (1)
	Gene drive	0	0	0	0	0	1 (1)	0	1 (0)	0	0	0	0
	Genome editing	0	3 (3)	0	0	0	0	0	20 (4)	2 (1)	0	0	3 (3)
	In vitro meat	1 (0)	2 (0)	0	0	0	0	0	8 (1)	3 (0)	0	0	1 (0)
	Nitrogen fixing bacteria	3 (0)	2 (1)	7 (2)	1 (1)	0	3 (2)	1 (0)	1 (0)	1 (0)	0	0	0
Integrative technology	Regenerative agriculture	12 (4)	13 (5)	1 (1)	2 (0)	1 (0)	3 (0)	1 (0)	23 (2)	13 (0)	2 (1)	0	9 (1)
Robot Farmers	Bio-refinery	0	1 (0)	0	0	0	0	0	1 (0)	1 (0)	0	0	0
	Farm automation	1(1)	0	0	0	1 (1)	0	0	1 (1)	1 (1)	0	0	0
Rural-Urban	Vertical farm	0	2 (0)	0	0	0	0	0	5 (3)	0	0	0	1 (0)
Transparent Food	Hyperspectral imaging	0	2 (0)	0	0	0	1 (0)	0	21 (7)	6 (2)	0	0	1 (0)
	Total	35 (7)	131 (18)	48 (17)	8 (2)	8 (5)	43 (8)	5 (1)	354 (54)	93 (11)	2 (1)	32 (5)	42 (7)

Note: Numbers in parentheses indicate studies considered relevant after thorough content review. The dates on which the search was conducted are presented in Table A2 in the Appendix. Technologies for which there is no scientific record of their impact on the SJOS domains have been omitted from the table.

Figure 1. Frequency of Records of Interrelation between Technology Clusters and SJOS Dimensions.

3.2.2. Technology Contributions to SJOS Domains

3.2.2.1. Climate Change, Chemical Pollution and Aerosol Loading

Agriculture is one of the economic sectors that directly and indirectly contributes to climate change and contribute to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Balafoutis et al., 2017). At the same time, climate change greatly affects agricultural production. Agricultural innovations play a crucial role in addressing the complex and multifaceted challenges posed by climate change, including side effects such as the increasing experience of droughts, floods and extreme weather conditions. Recent developments also present a promising solution to chemical pollution, including particulate matter, which threatens crop and animal health and has additionally been shown to negatively affect human health (Arias et al., 2021). Some of these emerging technological developments with a potential to mitigate climate change, chemical pollution and aerosol loading are presented below.

3.2.2.2. Decision Tools

Studies in the literature (e.g., Finger et al., 2019; Capmourteres et al., 2018; Dayioglu & Turker, 2021; Balafoutis et al., 2017; Schieffer & Dillon, 2015) show that decision tool technologies provide several environmental benefits, including the application of inputs with fewer losses of fertilizers and pesticides to the environment and reduced greenhouse gas emissions. For example, a recently developed decision support system to analyze tractor guidance technology calculates carbon footprint reduction due to decrease in fuel and agricultural chemicals (Lindsay et al., 2018). The efficiency of decision support systems can be significantly improved by big data, Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI). This combination provides farmers with predictive insights and detailed recommendations for operational and strategic decision-making. Various AI-based decision support

systems that have been developed for farm management, manure management, crop production, pest management, irrigation, yield and variety selection, and disease control, reduce the carbon footprint of agriculture (Lakshmi & Corbett, 2023) and pushes agricultural practices towards sustainable farming (Rejeb et al., 2022). These technologies have monitoring and control functions that help farmers reduce, e.g., energy and fuel consumption (Dayioglu & Turker, 2021), leading to a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (Dayioglu et al., 2021).

Decision tools are not only used in mitigation strategies but are also an important tool for adaptation to climate change. For example, big data and machine learning help farmers to find the climate change adaptation strategy (Mulla et al., 2019) by providing insights to rainfall and temperature patterns (Arora et al., 2022) and in forecasting agricultural yields based on climate condition in specific areas (Cedric et al., 2022).

The application of synthetic materials in agriculture contributes to diverse forms of pollution and has a far-reaching effect on the environment. Decision tools combining with advanced image analysis techniques have the potential to reduce the impact of chemical pollutants on the environment. The study of Dayioglu & Turker (2021), specifically, mentions big data, artificial intelligence, machine learning and the Internet of Things as new technologies that can prevent chemical pollution. For example, IoT technologies enhance pests and insects control by precise tracking, simulation, and disease prediction (Dayioglu & Turker, 2021). A synergy of decision support systems and artificial intelligence allow efficient application of pesticides and fertilizers in agriculture production (del Águila et al., 2015). The authors underscore that decision support systems provide pest management guidelines and regulations. AI-enabled systems can automatically assess crop growth and alert the probabilities of pest attacks (Subeesh & Mehta, 2021). Cavan et al. (2023) in their study showed that, decision support system can be harnessed also as indicators for pollution risks by nitrogen fertilizers and pesticides.

3.2.2.3. Gene Change

Breeding strategies are imperative in the pursuit of improving animal production to feed the expected 9 billion global population by 2030 amidst infectious diseases and a looming threat from climate change. Genome editing tools offer a pragmatic solution to achieving the desired goal of addressing food security and sustainable food production as captured in the sustainable development agenda (Whitworth et al., 2022). For example, gene editing improves production traits to reduce environmental impact (Whitworth et al., 2022). According to Pereira et al., (2020) the use of bioinoculants plays a significant role in mitigating climate change in agricultural production. Genetic manipulation via inhibition of soil nitrification by plant roots exudation mitigates greenhouse gas emissions (Ogawa et al., 2021; Subarao et al., 2017).

Chemical pollution (i.e., novel entities) is focused on synthetic materials or genetic materials related to chemical pollution. Trends in agricultural production seek sustainable practices that can improve crop adaptation and production and reduce application of external inputs such as synthetic pesticides and fertilizers (Pereira et al., 2020). Excessive use of chemical fertilizers contributes to the greenhouse effect and depletion of the ozone layer (Panpatte et al., 2018). A change in pH and sodium chloride concentration caused by the application of chemical fertilizers and pesticides to the soil reduces the physiological activity of nitrogen-fixing bacteria such as *Azotobacter* (Panpatte et al., 2018). According to Mrkovacki et al., (2002), as cited by Panpatte et al., (2018), glyphosate containing pesticides reduces the respiration rate of *Azotobacter chroococcum*, a nitrogen-fixing bacteria, by 60%. Accordingly, selenium (Se) biofortification inhibits the content of heavy metal elements and improves yield and quality in agricultural crops (Liang et al., 2021). Gene drive as pest control (Jones & Brown, 2023) and the use of bacteriophage (Huang & Nitin, 2020) in agriculture are promoted mechanisms that reduce the use of synthetic chemical pesticides as control measures against crop pests.

3.2.2.4. Integrative Technology

Regenerative agriculture promises zero carbon farming or even offsetting GHG emissions from other sectors. Despite a growing number of scientific studies, scientific uncertainty persists about the effects of regenerative agricultural practices on carbon sequestration (Tan & Kuebbing, 2023; Giller et al., 2021). However, literature provide evidence that reduced fertilization in combination with the use of cover crops led to reduction of GHG emissions at the farm-level (Schreefel et al., 2022). In livestock production, review of Jordon et al. (2022) suggests that adoption of the regenerative agriculture practices on grazing land has potential to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions associated with ruminant farming by increasing livestock productivity. Moreover, employing principles of regenerative agriculture, can contribute to the increased climate resilience (Bracken et al., 2023).

3.2.2.5. Robot Farmers¹

The emergence of agriculture 4.0 in the agricultural sector has led to the use of sensors and robotics for most farm operations. Agrochemical applications contribute to emissions and, subsequently, to climate change. The use of robots for mechanical weeding reduces the incidence of pesticide use without facing a trade-off of high emissions (Bocker et al., 2019). A study by Karen et al. (2018) shows that fertilizer application with low-cost automated machines with lower horsepower and fuel consumption leads to savings in greenhouse gas emissions.

3.2.3. Biodiversity

Changes in farming systems over last decades, especially intensification, concentration, and specification, have been identified as main drivers of the biodiversity loss. The challenge for new technologies is to prevent biodiversity loss or even to enhance biodiversity.

3.2.3.1. Decision Tools

Decision tools provide the potential to increase biodiversity by reducing fertilizer and pesticide consumption and soil compaction (Rezaei et al., 2018). According to Gackstetter et al. (2023), the integration of new technologies (decision support systems, sensors, AI, and big data) in autonomous field management can improved both productivity and environmental sustainability. Decision tools that can integrate current crop and weather knowledge with information on likely responses to fertilizers and pesticides have the potential to support optimal management regimes that minimize biodiversity loss.

3.2.3.2. Gene Change

Biofortification plays an important role in dietary diversity and sustainable food-based approaches. For example, focusing biofortification on neglected or underutilized species rather than staple foods contributes to an improvement in the activities of plant genetic resources for human food (Johns & Eyzaguirre, 2007).

3.2.3.3. Integrative Technology

Regenerative agriculture as an alternative to current farming system addresses the challenge to reduce negative impact of agricultural production on soil degradation, water quality and biodiversity of flora and fauna (van Eekeren et al., 2022). The concept of regenerative agriculture relies on natural processes to increase the biodiversity and resilience of farming systems, e.g., the inclusion of clover in grass-mixtures (R. de Haas et al., 2019), diverse crop rotation, and agroforestry (Giller et al., 2021).

¹ The sources of literature used for the robot farmers discussion were not part of the search results for robotic farming and climate change but were relevant for robot farming despite retrieved from decision tools and the climate search outcome.

Regenerative agriculture generates agricultural products, sequesters carbon, enriches soils, improves watersheds, enhances ecosystem services and biodiversity (Giller et al., 2021).

3.2.3.4. Robot Farmers

The advent of smart agriculture has paved the way for lessening the burden of anthropogenic activities on agricultural land and, subsequently, improving biodiversity and ecosystems. Robot farmers enable more diverse agroecological farming without agrochemicals, and thus eliminate land sharing by reconciling yields and biodiversity (Daum, 2021). Despite the benefits of robot farming in addressing the challenges of biodiversity and the environment, it has the downside of diminishing human judgment, conventional knowledge, and farming experiences. Additionally, it can undermine people's ability to nurture ecosystems (ETC group, 2023).

3.2.4. Nutrient Flow

Nutrient availability plays an important role in agricultural productivity, food security, and sustainable development. Nutrient deficiency in plants can lead to less biomass production and reduced yield. However, increasing nutrient (e.g., nitrogen) levels through external production inputs, such as fertilizers, that results in higher productivity level, can cause a series of environmental pollution issues and even diminished yields when fertilization become excessive (Arias et al., 2021). Emerging technologies face the challenge of balancing production and environmental impact.

3.2.4.1. Decision Tools

Higher yields are often achieved by intensive practices with large amounts of fertilizer. However, excessive and unbalanced fertilizer application leads to low nutrient use efficiency and high environmental risks (Jiang et al., 2019). Decision tools such as machine learning (Flynn et al., 2023), AI (Ganeshkumar et al., 2021), Internet of Things (Subeesh & Mehta, 2021; Kale & Sonavane, 2019) in combination with hyperspectral remote sensing can help make nutrient (e.g., nitrogen and phosphorus) application smarter. These technologies analyze the data obtained by monitoring nitrogen and phosphorus content and the biological characteristics of the vegetation, resulting in a recommendation of the amount of fertilizer to be applied. The simulations that these technologies perform (e.g., plant growth and soil processes) enable optimization of management practices and consequently improve production and agronomic efficiency (Jiang et al., 2019). Decision support systems utilizes these technologies provide optimal nutrient management that synchronizes fertilization application with plant nutrient utilization, which maximizes crop yield and quality, increases profit, conserves resources, enhances soil quality and productivity, and ensuring long term food security (Xu et al., 2021; Pahmeyer et al., 2021; Kropp et al., 2019; Prabakaran et al., 2018; Papadopoulos et al., 2011).

3.2.4.2. Gene Change

Nutrient flow (also geochemical flow) covers agricultural practices that use chemical fertilizers, mainly nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. These reactive elements cause environmental losses, for example, loss of soil nutrients (de Souza et al., 2016). Consequently, the high dependence of modern agriculture on an excessive, imbalanced, and constant synthetic input of chemical fertilizers causes deterioration of soil quality (Giri et al., 2019). To change the narrative of these agricultural models, technologies that ensure a diversity of soil management techniques, for example nitrogen-fixing rhizobacteria (PGPR) inoculation, contribute to reducing the use of chemical fertilizers and ensure an increase of approximately 88% in grain yield (de Souza et al., 2016). In another study, Chugh et al., (2022) emphasized that nanotechnology, an integral part of biofortification, ensures efficient uptake of nutrients, minimizes waste, and overuse, thus improving soil and plant health.

3.2.4.3. Integrative Technology

Regenerative agriculture, that is generally understood either as practices such as minimizing soil disturbance, integrating livestock, maximizing soil cover, rotational grazing, and lowering external inputs, enhances ecosystem processes such as water, nutrient, and carbon cycles (Bless et al., 2023). According to Musto et al. (2023), this concept has the potential to significantly increase soil organic carbon levels, restore functional ecosystem processes and healthy soils, leading to greater system resilience and crop productivity and thereby ultimately address the challenges of soil degradation and dependence on intensive use of agrochemicals.

3.2.4.4. Robot Farmers

Manual farm operations continue to exist in rural developing areas despite the benefits of farm automation and the use of sensors and drones in the agricultural sector. Aside from the potential benefits of robotic farming, no studies were found on the relationship and / or impact of geochemical flow and robot farmers.

3.2.5. Land and Water Use

The agricultural sector is responsible for about 70% of global freshwater consumption (Chen et al., 2018). Changes in weather patterns due to climate change are raising increasing concerns about potential changes in water availability. Failure to adopt good water management practices can significantly affect the food security of a region. Agricultural innovation contributes to proper assessment and management of the quantity and quality of available water resources (Arias et al., 2021). They also address the need to optimize land use (Mompremier et al., 2022).

3.2.5.1. Decision Tools

Artificial intelligence (incorporating machine learning, big data etc.) algorithms play important role in determining amount of groundwater and/or freshwater available in the soil for agricultural activities (Azzam et al., 2022). In a study by Arora et al. (2022), the authors state that the integration of big data in agriculture offers valuable insights into rainfall patterns and water cycles. These insights can be further used in decision support systems to ensure water-efficient agriculture (Mulla et al., 2019). Internet of Things technologies that enables data-driven irrigation practices can also improve water use efficiency (Tsolakis et al., 2023). The IoT-based smart irrigation systems calculate the precise needs for water employing sensors that measures relative humidity, soil moisture, temperature, light intensity, etc., provide real-time automatic irrigation and remote manual irrigation for different growth phases (Dayioglu & Turker, 2021).

Decision tools have also potential to promote agricultural production through optimal land use. For example, decision support systems (especially those that integrate functionalities of GIS) address various questions related to yield response to land use and land management practices (including irrigation optimization) (Mompremier et al., 2022).

3.2.5.2. Gene Change

The conversion of land to agricultural soils and other uses affects biodiversity and the ecosystem. Degraded land has the lowest population of nitrogen-fixing bacteria relative to other ecosystems. This is triggered by the lack of vegetation in degraded soils that have the lowest organic content (Anggrainy et al., 2020). Improving groundwater resource quality is a critical environmental concern for the continuous improvement of rural communities' quality of life. In a study conducted to examine the origin of microbiological contamination of groundwater, Valenzuela et al., (2009) pointed out the importance of bacteriophage in providing information about fecal microorganisms reaching groundwater, which helps to detect infected groundwater consumed by rural communities.

3.2.5.3. Robot Farmers

The introduction of innovative technologies such as the Internet of Things in agricultural operations, particularly access and use of water, has been of concern to policy makers in addressing the challenges of sustainable water in the agricultural sector. A report by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, as cited in Tsolakis et al. (2023), documents 67% water savings with the application of drones in precision irrigation. In structured farmland, field robots are found to work best, and this influences farmers' decisions to structure their farms. This, in turn, helps reduce farm and landscape diversity, thereby improving land management in the agricultural sector (Daum, 2021).

3.2.6. Nutritional Security

Nutritional security is defined as a situation “when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to food which is safe and consumed in sufficient quantity and quality to meet their dietary needs and food preferences, and is supported by an environment of adequate sanitation, health services and care, allowing for a healthy and active life” (Committee on World Food Security, 2017). Nutritional security can benefit from agricultural innovations. From a public perspective, global nutritional security is even often cited as a major driver for further technological advancements (Wolfert et al., 2017).

3.2.6.1. Decision Tools

Decision tools can empower nutritional security in several ways. The Internet of Things, for example, allows farmers to increase their technical knowledge of agricultural production, enabling them to use production inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides more efficiently. Digital technologies such as blockchain, big data analysis and artificial intelligence are increasing the complex production capacity of agriculture and improving the overall efficiency of the agri-food industry (Liu & Liu, 2023; Kutyauro et al., 2023; Tamasiga et al., 2023; Jimenez et al., 2020; Pathan et al., 2020; Zhai et al., 2020; Lagos-Ortiz et al., 2019).

Artificial intelligence is transforming agriculture to be more reliable, efficient and predictive. For example, AI allows for automating the identification of plant and animal disease and improve the accuracy of disease identification (Nigam et al., 2021). Machine learning using ultra-scale images and computer vision combined with GPS to classify crops, gathering information on their size, safety, quality, allows to reduce use of pesticides and fertilizers, e.g., to apply the best chemical at the optimal dose only to individual weeds (Bloomer et al., 2024), and more efficient harvest time (Awuchi, 2023). Big data and deep learning are contributing to accurate and non-destructive yield estimation at the plot level, which has significant potential to accelerate and revolutionize crop breeding to meet the growing demand for food (Bhadra et al., 2023).

Digital technologies are also finding applications in reducing food waste. For example, artificial intelligence is helping to reduce food waste due to inadequate safety measures. Machine learning can predict animal sources of salmonella and trace foodborne illness to its source (Awuchi, 2023). Another technology to which the literature attributes the potential to prevent food waste is the blockchain by improving traceability and transparency throughout the food supply chain (Xu et al., 2020; Antonucci et al., 2019).

3.2.6.2. Gene Change

Over the next three decades, the world's human population is projected to increase by 25%, reaching a staggering 10 billion (Sagar, 2023; Chaturvedi & Srinivas, 2019). Consequently, the demand for essential resources such as food, fodder, energy, and diversified food consumption is expected to increase. In response to this pressing challenge, global agricultural output, covering both crops and animals, will need to increase by 60% to meet the increasing demands of the future population (Maximiano et al., 2021). Gene change technologies such as breeding, genome editing are among the

technologies to bridge the gap between food supply and nutritional security in the agricultural sector (Sagar, 2023; Wray-Cahen et al., 2022). For example, Siebert et al., (2022) noted that genome editing lessens the world hunger problem (i.e., food security) by 26.1% as a natural technology. Furthermore, in vitro technology stands out as a promising innovation capable of regulating the fat content in meat to align with current dietary standards (Wyatt, 2014). In the literature, biofortification has received attention as a technological strategy to combat micronutrient deficiency with its attractive cost-effective and sustainable nature (Sandhu et al., 2023; Guindon et al., 2021; Lividini & Fiedler 2015; Shohag et al., 2011). In a similar literature, Azadi et al., (2022) underscored that biofortification improves food utilization due to its ability to increase the levels of essential nutrients in food.

3.2.6.3. Integrative Technology

Meeting future food demand while avoiding destructive side-effects can be achieved not only through high-tech agriculture such as digital and genotype breeding technologies, but also through a radical shift towards nature-based solutions. Regenerative agriculture represents such a nature-based agricultural system (Gremmen, 2022), whose processes have the potential to reduce reliance on off-farm inputs such as synthetic and mineral fertilizers, chemical pesticides, and herbicides, while maintaining yields. In other words, this system promotes resource efficiency (Voisin et al., 2024).

3.2.6.4. Robot Farmers

Advancements in technology offer the agricultural sector an opportunity to take advantage of in-field data for informed decision-making in resource-intensive operations. Through automated guided machines, farmers can make informed choices regarding precision irrigation planning and ultimately increase resource use efficiency and crop productivity (Tsolakis et al., 2023). The study of Gill et al., (2023) showed that robotic systems reduce the proliferation of weeds through selective mechanical weeding, and this improves crop productivity and subsequently food production levels.

3.2.6.5. Rural-Urban

In meeting the growing demand for food, vertical farming can help overcome the limitations of the production potential of arable land and satisfy preferences for local hyper-fresh food (Eaves & Eaves, 2018). According to Carolan (2023), it can be view as a strategy to enhance national food independence.

Vertical farming is a closed system that is designed to maximize production density, productivity, and resource use efficiency (Graamans et al., 2018). It focuses primarily on fruit and vegetables and aims to supply consumers with these local products of high nutritional value all year round. Local production has significant nutritional advantages over transported produce. It is known that the nutritional value of fruit and vegetables decreases during transport, even if they are refrigerated. Compared to greenhouses, plants are grown in multi-level racks with hydroponic systems and only with artificial light in vertical farming systems. This dramatically increases the yield per square meter (Eaves & Eaves, 2018). Moreover, uniformity of interior climate in terms of lighting, temperature and relative humidity increases the quality of production (Graamans et al., 2018). In addition, the low space requirements make it possible to locate these systems close to urban centers (Eaves & Eaves, 2018). However, current solutions are highly energy intensive (Graamans et al., 2018). The debate whether it can compete with greenhouse farming taking advantage of the sun does not have a clear conclusion yet.

3.2.6.6. Transparent Food

Hyperspectral imaging can contribute to nutritional security in several ways. For example, by classifying crop varieties and identifying superior varieties with high yields (Meng et al., 2022) or through a combination of drought-tolerant varieties and accurate monitoring of water availability, irrigation practices can be optimized to ensure sustained yield increases and food security for communities in drought-prone areas (Arias et al., 2021). The study of Xia et al. (2019) highlights its

application in determination of the germination condition and viability of seeds prior to cultivate, sale and plant. It is especially suitable and powerful for inspecting quality and safety of various food and agricultural products (Ma et al., 2023; Li et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2012). For example, in cereal production it can identify various contaminants in cereal grains that is an important step to identify the grade of the grain (Ravikanth et al., 2016). It also offers a promising solution for preventing crop damage and production losses caused by diseases, as it captures detailed information on the chemical and physical characteristics of agricultural crops and provides information on diseased and defective crops (Noshiri et al., 2023).

3.2.7. Farm Resilience, Economy and Social Equity

Innovation in technology present an opportunity for the agricultural sector to leverage its benefits to promote sustainable development goals. Modern agricultural technologies are improving yield quantity and quality, reducing production cost, increasing farmers' socio-economic status.

3.2.7.1. Decision Tools

Digital technologies such as cloud and edge computing, blockchain, AI, big data and Internet of Things could contribute to an overall increase in the competitiveness, sustainability, and resilience of the agricultural sector (Gebresenbet et al., 2023). For example, AI can help reduce input usage and increase agricultural productivity (Ganeshkumar et al., 2021). Internet of Things also aims to enhance productivity of agricultural activities and handle the instability of prices. For example, in livestock production, AI and Internet of Things helps to raise yields by monitoring health, welfare (including optimal environment) and productive capacity of animals (Arora et al., 2022). Blockchain strengthens the competitive potential of farmers to access markets (SgROI, 2022) by reducing information asymmetry between farmers and markets, helping farmers gain more comprehensive information about market transactions (Liu & Liu, 2023), and providing them with pricing power and income potential (Nandhini et al., 2023).

Decision tools enables farms to increase their resilience in response to risky nature of agricultural production (Tamasiga et al., 2023). As digital technologies enable efficient and effective monitoring of changes in agricultural productivity over time and space, for example through remote sensing and sensors on machinery, they enable more cost-effective insurance solutions. Moreover, digital twins and AI offer new opportunities for farmers to understand and identify failure sources and establish prediction systems and early warning mechanisms. For example, crop and animal health can be modelled and predicted more effectively, thereby reducing the likelihood and magnitude of the impact of shocks on the performance of farming systems (Finger, 2023). Big data technologies can also help farmers accurately manage risk and address supply imbalances (Arora et al., 2022).

3.2.7.2. Gene Change

Genome editing techniques have received a lot of attention in the literature as one of the most effective innovations. Achieving the goal of zero hunger by 2030 and meeting the nutritional needs of the global population demands increased and sustained levels of both crop and animal production. In the crop sector, gene-edited crops are considered high yielding and resistant to climate variations and thus contribute to sustainable food production (Ahmad et al., 2021). Studies show that animals developed from genetic engineering have resistance to diseases and pests, thereby reducing the need for antibiotics or insecticides (Wray-Cahen et al., 2022). Furthermore, gene-edited animals are more resilient to the effects of climate change and environmental challenges (Bai & Plastow 2022: Wray-Cahen et al., 2022). Bai & Plastow (2022) underscored the efficiency and cost effectiveness of genome editing tools, highlighting their significant potential for future animal production, particularly in developing resistance to diseases.

3.2.7.3. Integrative Technology

Literature suggests that regenerative agriculture can achieve win–win scenarios: improving ecosystem services while increasing on-farm profits as well (Loring, 2022). According to Dipu et al. (2022), regenerative agriculture is a promising pathway for building ecological and social resilience within food systems. It has potential to increase agricultural productivity (Jordon et al., 2022) and minimizes pressures associated with industrial agricultural production systems, such as economic concentration within the food industry, and fragmentation of rural communities (Dipu et al., 2022). For example, in livestock production, it is purported to increase livestock productivity (e.g., animal liveweight gain, milk production, or wool growth) and pasture carrying capacity via enhancing forage productivity (Jordon et al., 2022). Furthermore, regenerative agriculture also has a potential to restore the health of communities and farmers (Bless et al., 2023).

3.2.7.4. Robot Farmers

Robotic farming has been purported to ease farm operations in agriculture particularly with its precision and data-driven functionality. However, regarding farm resilience, economy, and social equity no relevant studies were identified.

3.2.8. Health

Emerging agricultural technologies that reduce the misuse of pesticides and chemical fertilizers help to reduce pesticide residues and other harmful components such as nitrates and cadmium in food. Although the decision tools seem to have the potential to reduce human health risk, no relevant human health study was found.

3.2.8.1. Gene Change

There is a growing interest in improving agricultural practices to increase the accessibility of nutrients to people. Selenium biofortification is one of the nutritional interventions that aim to address soil deficiencies and increase nutrient levels in crops to a point where it positively impacts human health (Wood & Baudron, 2018; Miller & Welch 2013). According to Nair et al., (2013), Selenium biofortification improves the antioxidant content of flavonoids and prevents cardiovascular and cancerous diseases. Maximiano et al., (2021), added that gene-edited crops have nutritional properties that help patients with chronic diseases (e.g., heart disease and cancer associated with high-fat diets). Green et al., (2016) pointed out that the status of iron, zinc, and vitamin A in humans that contribute to malnutrition can be improved using biofortification strategies.

3.2.8.2. Robot Farmers

The health and well-being of farmers continues to remain a major challenge in the agricultural sector in terms of manual farm input applications. The influx of agriculture 4.0 with robots and drones can prevent health damage by spraying pesticides on plants with the required amount (Thorat et al., 2023). On the contrary, tractor overturning accidents threaten the life and health of farmers and thus discourage farm automation in the agriculture sector (Watanabi & Sakai, 2019).

3.2.8.3. Transparent Food

Hyperspectral imaging offers a promising solution for detection of toxins in food, e.g., aflatoxin that is a serious threat to agricultural safety and human health. Combined with deep learning, which can extract higher-dimensional features in large datasets more efficiently than machine learning, the hyperspectral imaging can achieve more than 95% pixel-level detection accuracy for aflatoxin detection (Zhu et al., 2023).

3.3. Emerging Technologies with Documented Impact on SJOS

The search of the literature identified 13 promising technologies from 6 clusters of investigated technologies. From the cluster of decision tools, the scientific community's interest is mainly focused on artificial intelligence, decision support systems, and big data. Publications on big data and artificial intelligence also frequently mention the Internet of Things. Blockchain technology also appears to be promising, especially in nutritional security and economy. In addition, genome editing, biofortification, nitrogen-fixing bacteria, and in vitro culture within gene change technologies have been identified as promising. Similarly, in robotic farming, only farm automation appeared promising in the literature. Within the integrative technology cluster, the focus of academics is on regenerative agriculture. In the transparent food cluster, only hyperspectral imaging has been identified as a promising technology. Finally, within the rural-urban technology cluster, only vertical farming records were found.

3.3.1. Decision Tools

3.3.1.1. Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data, and Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The Internet of things is referred to a network of physical objects called 'things' (e.g., computing devices, sensors, appliances, and machines) with network connectivity that can enable these objects to collect and exchange data and interact with the environment (Abbasi et al., 2022). According to Matta & Pant (2019), it has a huge potential to become a game-changer in agriculture automation. The use of IoT supported by an efficient intelligent decision-making system can lead to a significant reduction of human intervention in various agricultural operations. The main goal of the IoT is to generate real-time data. This data, also referred to as Big Data, includes textual content (i.e., structured, semi-structured, and unstructured), and multimedia content (e.g., videos, images, audio) (Abbasi et al., 2022).

Agricultural big data typically originates from diverse sectors and stages within agricultural production. This data can be sourced from agricultural fields utilizing ground sensors, aerial vehicles, and ground vehicles equipped with specialized cameras and sensors. Additionally, governmental bodies contribute through reports and regulations, private organizations provide data through online web services, farmers contribute their knowledge through surveys, and social media platforms offer further sources of information. On-farm data relates to detailed production practices, input use, disease outbreaks, food safety concerns, and yields. The data collected is stored in a computerized database and then processed using computer algorithms. Machine learning tools, specifically, are employed for tasks such as prediction, clustering, and classification, enabling deeper analysis and insights (Abbasi et al., 2022).

Artificial intelligence can be used to give meaningful insights from the data which can lead to high-quality decision-making (Subeesh & Mehta, 2021). It is a system that can perceive, learn, reason, communicate and act in the world, exhibit flexibility, ingenuity, creativity, real-time responsiveness, and long-term reasoning, use different approaches to representation or reasoning, and exhibit capabilities in complex environments and social contexts (Alexander et al., 2024). In agriculture, AI includes innovative technologies such as field sensors, drones, farm management software tools, automated machinery and water and fertilizer management solutions (Cavazza et al., 2023). The applications of AI in agriculture are wide-ranging, for example in relation to activities such as general crop management, pest control, disease control, weed control, agricultural product monitoring and storage control, soil management and irrigation, and yield forecasting (Figiel, 2022).

The benefits of artificial intelligence and resulting automation of farming practices, includes increased accuracy and rapidity of plant diagnosis, cost savings, efficient energy consumption, and improved product quality. Furthermore, AI can enhance agricultural production, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, ensure animal welfare, improve field navigation, and boost the performance of agricultural robots. Implementing AI in the agri-food sector faces several obstacles, including social issues of AI,

such as replacing humans in the workforce and unemployment; technical issues - lack of connectivity and security attacks; legal issue, such as data privacy and ethical concerns; organizational barriers, such as resistance to change and the need for new skills and capabilities; and economic barriers related to prohibitive investment costs and uncertainty about the value of AI in the agri-food industry (Rejeb et al., 2022). In addition, field monitoring with sensors is often labour intensive (Atkinson et al. 2019), and real-time management decisions at field levels require a unified approach to model the condition of crops in crop production (Storm et al. 2024; Kersebaum et al. 2015).

3.3.1.2. Blockchain

Blockchain can be defined as a distributed database of transactions, ledgers, and digital occurrences that provides a decentralized platform that serves as an immutable platform for participating parties. There are numerous applications for blockchain, ranging from financial transactions, manufacturing, logistics, and supply chain management (Moosavi et al., 2021). Recent studies highlight the role of blockchain in supply chain management. In agri-food supply chain, the blockchain can be used to ensure authenticity of food safety and quality (Antonucci et al., 2019).

3.3.1.3. Decision Support Systems

A decision support system can be defined as a smart system that supports decision-making to specific problems by providing operational answers to users based on useful information extracted from raw data, documents, personal knowledge, and models (Abbasi et al., 2022). These systems are based on supervised algorithms that require robust and reliable training data sets. In the agriculture domain, data collection may be complicated or even unavailable. Thus, the historical documentation that exists suffers from gaps and lacks standardization (Rozenstein et al., 2024).

3.3.2. Gene Change

Gene change technologies (e.g., gene editing) are being heralded as potent tools for developing agricultural products and foods with a diverse range of benefits. Gene change innovations include but not limited to genome editing, biofortification, bacteriophage, gene drive, in-vitro culture, nitrogen fixing bacteria and transgenic organisms.

3.3.2.1. Genome Editing

Genome editing (also gene editing) is an advanced molecular biology technique that facilitates precision breeding (Ogawa et al., 2021). To meet the needs of the growing global population, the application of gene editing techniques is essential to increase crop yield and ensure sufficient food levels (Bain et al., 2019). Gene editing techniques induce resistance in plants to harsh environmental conditions (Sagar, 2023). Additionally, they confer adaptation traits to both plants and animals in response to climate change, while also enhancing crop quality and diversifying products (De Souza et al., 2022). Although gene editing has many benefits, public skepticism and debate over genetically modified organisms continue to impact the acceptance of gene edited products (Bain et al., 2019). According to the American Seed Trade Association as cited by Bain et al., (2019), "without gene editing, the food security situation would worsen globally, especially in developing countries."

3.3.2.2. Biofortification

Biofortification refers to the process of producing genetically improved food crops that are rich in essential micronutrients, through traditional breeding or genetic modification (Johns & Enyazaguirre, 2007). Vaiknoras et al., (2019) also sees biofortification as a process by which staple foods are fortified to increase the micronutrient content. The global concern about malnutrition and hidden hunger, particularly in developing countries, has led policy makers and stakeholders to develop interventions to address the problem. A plethora of studies emphasize the importance of prioritizing micronutrients in foods as a critical driver of human growth and development (Sandhu et al., 2023; Okello et al., 2019).

Biofortification provides a promising remedy for addressing global malnutrition and hidden hunger. Sandhu et al., (2023) in their study on the integration of biofortification in crops for sustainable agricultural development and nutritional security pointed out that biofortification reduces global-scale malnutrition among people. The challenge associated with biofortification in contemporary agriculture has been linked to the maintenance of nutritional quality and quantity (yield per hectare of grains), as well as storage capacity (e.g., staples containing carotenoids) along the agricultural value chain (Nkhata et al., 2020).

3.3.2.3. Nitrogen-Fixing Bacteria

Nitrogen-fixing bacteria are biological reactions in which microorganisms convert atmospheric nitrogen gas into ammonia gas (Chennappa et al., 2018). The notion of reducing external inputs such as pesticides and synthetic fertilizers in agriculture due to its negative impact on climate change and the environment continues to attract policy discussions across different disciplines. Nitrogen-fixing bacteria are an alternative to the use of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium fertilizers (de Souza et al., 2016) and reduce nutrients by leaching, denitrification, and volatilization (Thomas & Singh, 2019). As biofertilizers and growth catalyst, nitrogen fixing bacteria of rhizobia are often used as growth promote leguminous crops (Thomas & Singh, 2019).

3.3.2.4. Bacteriophage

Bacteriophage, sometimes called phage, is a naturally occurring biopesticide that is used to reduce the use of chemical pesticides and to treat and prevent infectious diseases (Smirnov et al., 2020). They are also recognized as a potential antibacterial agent against plant and human pathogenic bacteria. It has been reported as a food safety measure before and after harvest, as well as against plant pathogens (Huang & Nitin, 2020). In medicine, bacteriophages are used as antimicrobial drugs in the cases of septic diseases and bacterial infections of the gastrointestinal tract. In the agricultural sector, phages ensure the growth of production segments of natural and organic products, fight antibiotic resistance, limit the use of antibiotics, and ensure increased safety and functional efficiency of processing aids (Smirnov et al., 2020).

3.3.2.5. In Vitro Culture

In vitro culture, also known as cellular farming, involves deriving processed meat products directly from muscle tissue cultured in a nutrient medium as opposed to live animals (Chiles, 2013). Cellular farming uses less energy than conventional meat production and has lower greenhouse gas emissions (Chiles, 2013). Additionally, cellular farming increases animal welfare, reduces environmental costs, and sustains and enhances human health through food provision (Moyano-Fernández, 2023; Mattick et al., 2015). The potential of in vitro culture has attracted a lot of policy discussions on meat production and human overconsumption. However, the concept of in vitro technology is hampered by the cost of the production process and the price of the product (Wyatt, 2014). Acceptance of in vitro culture is another barrier to its viability and existence, people are skeptical and do not equate the taste and texture of in vitro meat with more conventional meat due to the production process (Wyatt, 2014).

3.3.3. Integrative Technology

3.3.3.1. Regenerative agriculture

Regenerative agriculture is a low external input agriculture associated with a number of specific technologies and systems including nitrogen fixation, nutrient cycling, integrated nutrient management, crop rotation, integrated pest management and weed cycling that aim to produce highly nutritional food, free from biocides, at high yields (Giller et al., 2021). While the phrases "Regenerative Agriculture" and "Regenerative Farming" have been in use since the early 1980s, it is only recently that they have begun to capture widespread public interest. Today, regenerative agriculture is under

scrutiny for its potential as an economically viable middle-ground between high-input conventional agricultural systems and organic systems (Musto et al., 2023). By integrating elements of both conventional and organic farming systems, regenerative agriculture presents opportunities to transition away from heavy reliance on synthetic inputs and addresses existing challenges of conventional agricultural systems (Musto et al., 2023). From a philosophical perspective, regenerative agriculture is a biomimetic technology, and an example of the “(re)turn to nature” approach (Gremmen, 2022).

The core of regenerative agriculture is a commitment to improving the ecological (and sometimes social) outcomes of agricultural practices, typically commencing with the improvement of soil health as a fundamental step towards addressing concerns surrounding climate change, water quality, land productivity, and biodiversity conservation (Loring, 2022). Thus, most regenerative agriculture practices focus primarily on soil management and place a strong emphasis on augmenting soil carbon levels, under the premise that it will increase crop yields and mitigate climate change (Giller et al., 2021). Processes associated with regenerative agriculture are summarized in Newton et al. (2020) and Voisin et al. (2024). The key processes include tillage reduction, crop diversification, livestock management and integration.

The practices of regenerative agriculture improve soil health and re-carbonize the terrestrial biosphere, whilst minimizing synthetic chemical inputs, water use and greenhouse gas emissions. The study of Dipu et al. (2022) also highlights the potential of regenerative agriculture to build a socially just food system. However, it is important to note, that in order for regenerative agriculture to deliver claimed benefits, they need to be evaluated within the framework of the local environmental context (Giller et al., 2021).

Although regenerative agriculture has many benefits, its widespread adoption in agricultural practice is hampered by several barriers. Dipu et al. (2022) identified them as limited access to localized knowledge and mentoring; financial risk; and lack of supportive policies, including finance.

3.3.4. Robot Farmers

Robotic farming refers to the integration of robotic technologies and automation systems in agricultural practices. Daum (2021) define field robots as mobile, self-directed, decision-making, machines that perform crop production tasks under human supervision, without direct human labor. This innovative approach aims to improve efficiency, precision, and productivity as well as improve biosecurity in agriculture (Astill et al., 2020). The components of robotic farming include autonomous machines, drones, and robotic devices to perform tasks such as planting, harvesting, weeding, and monitoring crops.

3.3.4.1. Farm automation

In recent times, farm automation has taken the forefront as an alternative to human labor in agriculture due to the difficulty in recruiting and retaining human labor. Robotics provide economic benefits in the areas of crop scouting and mechanical weeding (Lowenberg-DeBoer et al., 2020). Coupled with other robotic devices, farm automation combines agricultural machinery, computer systems, electronics, and data management to improve field operations. In the existing literature, da Silveira et al. (2021) pointed out discrimination against farmers who are not digitally literate as challenges of robotic farming. The authors also stressed that the cost of acquiring technologies and the integration of a set of technologies to operationalize large databases for decision-making is a challenge for users. Apart from these, farm automation has ended family farming which previously existed and benefited from labor supervision and ensured farm coordination (Daum, 2021).

3.3.5. Rural-Urban

3.3.5.1. Vertical farming

Vertical farming is a production system where plants are grown indoors in multiple level racks using hydroponic systems and artificial light only. Utilizing multiple tiers of growing units minimizes the facility's footprint, thereby cutting down the expenses associated with locating close or within urban areas. This enables farmers to provide fresher products for consumers and the working experience for the employees (Eaves & Eaves, 2018). Vertical farming can achieve high productivity by adapting the interior climate to achieve uniform lighting, temperature and relative humidity through minimizing the interaction with the exterior climate. Limiting this interaction can also benefit the efficient use of energy, water and CO₂ (Graamans et al., 2018).

A shortcoming of vertical farming is the need for artificial lighting for photosynthesis and energy for air conditioning (cooling and vapour removal, both relying on forced air circulation) and dehumidification (Graamans et al., 2017). This system is highly energy intensive. In order to achieve economic viability compared to greenhouse horticulture, the increased resource productivity and/or the value of additional services would have to outweigh the disadvantage of the absence of solar energy (Graamans et al., 2018).

3.3.6. Transparent Food

3.3.6.1. Hyperspectral imaging

Hyperspectral imaging is a technique that integrates spectroscopic and computer vision techniques to obtain spectral and spatial information simultaneously (Li et al., 2019). As a spectral sensing technique, it allows to study crop biophysical and biochemical properties, soil characteristics and crops classification as well monitor large fields of cultivation. Fundamental principle of hyperspectral imaging technique is summarized in Wu & Sun (2013).

In the context of precision agriculture, the integration of hyperspectral imaging offers significant benefits as a non-invasive observation and monitoring without disrupting the growth process of crops. Moreover, a single aerial hyperspectral image provides a higher volume of detailed information about the developmental progress and chemical composition of both the plants and soil, all achieved with less labor intensity compared to laboratory analysis of field samples. Hyperspectral imaging can be used to estimate various agriculturally important soil properties such as carbon content, heavy metals, salinity, pH and overall fertility. It can also detect fungal organisms and toxins in crops and food that hinder plant productivity, contribute to additional food waste and have adverse effects on human health when consumed (Arias et al., 2021). In addition, this technology finds application in evaluation of marketability of products. The advantages of this technique are a reduction of human labour and the risk of human error in the classification process, while eliminating destructive testing methods (Schmilovitch et al., 2014). On the other hand, it has a lower sensitivity compared to conventional methods (Zhu et al., 2023).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This concluding chapter synthesizes the extensive analysis, blending insights on emerging agricultural technologies on the future of agriculture. The findings emphasize the potential of technological innovations to reshape agricultural practices in alignment with the SJOS .

The study identified several emerging technologies that could redefine agricultural sector by improving efficiency, sustainability, and resilience. Artificial intelligence (AI) and Big Data are expected to revolutionize agricultural decision making by providing predictive analytics for crop management and resource optimization. The Internet of Things (IoT) enables the seamless collection and analysis of real-time agricultural data, promoting operational efficiency and supporting SJOS's goal of resource optimization. Furthermore, advanced tools, such as decision support systems and blockchain technology, are transforming agricultural transparency and operational workflows, aligning with the SJOS objectives of sustainable practices and market integrity and improving the agricultural value chain. Biotechnological advances, such as genome editing and biofortification, have a far-reaching impact to improve food security and crop resilience, directly contributing to the SJOS goals. Additionally, innovations such as nitrogen-fixing bacteria and farm automation technologies are positioned to reduce chemical use and labor, one of the major adverse effects on sustainable production and consumption, aligning with the sustainability and efficiency goals of SJOS. Furthermore, hyperspectral imaging and vertical agriculture technologies demonstrate a commitment to precision agriculture and innovative space utilization, which are crucial in addressing land use challenges and urban food production, further aligning with the SJOS objectives.

The outlook of emerging technologies in the agri-food sector requires an environment that balances innovation with safety, environmental stewardship, and market fairness. The EU can ensure that its agricultural sector remains competitive and sustainable by creating an enabling environment that encourages innovation while ensuring safety and sustainability, the sector is well positioned to meet the evolving demands of society and the environment, guided by the strategic objectives of the SJOS. Maximizing the full potential of technological advances requires effective participation of stakeholders at all levels and addressing barriers to technology adoption, such as access to knowledge and financial risks, to achieve the strategic objectives of SJOS and ensure a prosperous future for the agricultural sector.

This deliverable serves as the basis for future research in WP8. The review of the literature revealed a paucity of empirical evidence on the impacts of emerging technologies, highlighting their uncertain future trajectories, adoption rates, and broader impacts on society and the economy. In the subsequent research, expert panels will assess and extend the attained knowledge with regard to the technological and economic parameters of the technologies. They will also identify the most promising technologies in terms of their ability to fill critical gaps and drive transformative change by aligning agricultural practices with the principles of the SJOS. Expert panels will enable a differentiated assessment approach based on the climatic zone, the farming system, and spatial factors.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 101060075 for the European Commission. It does not necessarily reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

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7. APPENDIX

7.1. Table A1. Scan of Emerging Technologies

Technology	Description
3D Printed Food	By filling machines with macronutrients such as starch, protein and fat, recipes could be prepared by the printer and made ready-to-eat with appealing shapes and textures. The addition of flavors and smells can be programmed into the recipes, opening many different possibilities for food such as specific sizes or configurations. This appliance has the potential to overcome other kitchen devices by combining them into one, lowering food production costs, and helping to combat food shortages.
Acellular Meat Production	Unlike cellular-derived meats, which are made from living or once-living organisms, acellular meats are created with organic molecules that don't contain any living (or once-living) material in the final product. Acellular products don't require starter cells extracted from muscle biopsies. If the molecular structure of an acellular chicken nugget is the same as a nugget made of tissue harvested from an animal, is it still considered meat?
Aerial Imaging	Farmers are increasingly taking to the sky to keep tabs on their crops. While no one's leaving the ground, drones and satellites that monitor fields and gather data on everything from biomass and plant height to the presence of weeds and level of water saturation are soaring in popularity. What's more, aerial imaging devices can use geographic information system (GIS) technology to analyze the efficacy of irrigation plans and their effects on land degradation, erosion, and drainage. And visuals so sharp as to allow for the assessment of an individual plant's foliage are not only entirely possible—they're actively being used to detect pests and diseases so that crops can be saved from environmental threats. As for the differences between the use cases for drones and satellites, both can accomplish most of the critical functions of aerial imaging technology, but each have their pros and cons. Drones can typically capture and relay information faster, but they can be prohibitively expensive and can't cover large parcels of land at a time. Satellites can conduct spectral imagery to analyze chlorophyll and nitrogen content, but access and availability are sometimes limited due to outages and cloud cover.
Aerial Wireless Network	Using drones or balloon-based designs, it could partially solve the problem of limited internet access across the globe. In developing countries, it can dramatically increase access to useful information like weather forecast thereby optimizing agriculture processes on remote farms.
Agricultural Biotechnology	Emerging agriculture technology trend is in the use of biotechnology and genetic engineering. Using biotechnology, farmers produce crops that are more resilient and easier to control, resulting in less waste. Genetically modified crops can be developed to resist specific diseases or pests, reducing the need for invasive actions such as synthetic pesticides, and lessening a crop's environmental impact. New adaptations may result in plants that remove pollutants from the soil, further improving the sustainability and reducing a farm's environmental footprint. Ultimately, agricultural biotechnology can make crop development safer and easier while also improving profitability through yield and harvesting optimizations.
Agricultural Drone	Drones, also known as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), are becoming more and more common in the agricultural industry. Drones may scan a field from above and report on problems like pests, infections, and a lack of essential nutrients. This agricultural data gives farmers command over the state of their fields.

Technology	Description
Agricultural Linguistics Model	Based on patterns in environmental, atmospheric, and diagnostic sensor data, it is possible to create digitized models of global agriculture. However, having such a global software and hardware network requires the establishment of common ground protocols, shared databases, and transparent processes. Possible gains are numerous: precise simulation of crop yields based on genetic data and weather patterns, growing food tailored to genetic predispositions of consumers or hyper-local food production in programmable, urban micro-plantations.
Agricultural Robotics	Shortage of labor is a critical problem farmers face, and this is amplified in the case of large field operations. So, startups are manufacturing agricultural robots to assist farmers in fruit-picking, harvesting, planting, transplanting, spraying, seeding, and weeding. Farmers are increasingly relying on robots to automate repetitive tasks in the field. They deploy smart agricultural machines, such as autonomous and semi-autonomous tractors for harvesting. Tractors also come with auto-steer technology for easier navigation across the field. Moreover, robots are used in automated systems for livestock management as well. This includes automated weighing scales, incubators, milking machines, and auto feeders. Robots allow farmers to focus more on improving overall productivity, without having to worry about slow farm processes. They also prevent human-induced errors and provide convenience through automation.
Agro-waste Biodegradable Coating	Biodegradable coatings are typically made of water, oil, and wax. But there is a promising new method using agricultural byproducts and waste, such as orange peels, to develop a formula to extend the shelf life of fresh produce. Bio-based coatings are made of bio-raw materials, such as biogenic scrap, or bio-mass balance methods using bionaphtha, biogas, or even natural amino acids. Currently, the agro-waste coating is a promising new coating method using agricultural byproducts and waste to extend the shelf life of fresh produce. In the form of a spray, the main component of these new lacquers is a biopolymer resin extracted from byproducts, such as orange peels, that act as a thin film, like plastic films.
Algae-Based Meal Replacement	Meal replacements based on algae that contain a controlled quantity of calories and nutrients designed to substitute traditional food meals. Meal replacements formed from algae that contain a controlled quantity of calories and nutrients designed to substitute traditional solid food meals. Algae are the fastest growing plant organisms in nature and are a great alternative source of vitamins, proteins, and minerals. Algae have a lot of potential as a scalable food source, as they grow anywhere – often in vertical fermentation tanks – without using large amounts of land or water. In current experiments, lab-grown algal-based food shows no negative impact on the environment, nor residual waste discharged into the ecosystem.
Animal-Robot Interaction	Systems that interact intelligently with animals to entertain, exercise, and improve their lives. This remotely controlled interaction will enable animal owners to interact and care for their livestock (or even pets) remotely without requiring their around-the-clock physical presence.
Artificial Intelligence	Incorporating AI in agriculture provides farmers with real-time insights into their field conditions, allowing them to be proactive. AI offers predictive insights for forecasting weather data, crop yield, and prices, thereby aiding farmers to make informed decisions. Chatbots offer suggestions and input recommendations to farmers. AI and ML algorithms automate anomaly and disease recognition in plants and livestock. This enables timely detection and corrective response if required. Biotechnology also deploys ML algorithms for gene selection recommendations. Further, AI provides easy access to finance to farmers who are denied credit from banks through alternative credit scoring.

Technology	Description
Atmospheric Water Harvesting	A large portion of the total global water expenditure is used in agriculture. This resource is predicted to become more and more scarce. Using micro-netting, however, water can be harvested from moisture in the air, which is abundant. Water droplets form on the coated filaments of the net before they drip down into a collector. An alternative method channels air underground, creating condensed water through a rapid cooling process.
Augmented Reality Information Transfer	Augmented reality can provide a rich contextual learning environment and guidance beyond that of static printed manuals. Among other things, agriculture or gardening maintenance could become much simpler by following interactive, step-by-step instructions that overlay relevant information on the user's current view.
Automated Home Farming	Using computer-controlled actuators, farming could be automated by a robot like a 3D-printer at home. The robot would perform a variety of functions, including seeding, watering, fertilizing, and removing weeds alleviating the consumer's need to perform those tasks manually. This technology could make farming at home accessible to anyone, while alleviating the time requirement and reducing the level of knowledge and expertise that gardeners often require. Also, indoor farming could become more viable through Pink-LED technology, which uses less energy for lighting.
Autonomous Agriculture Vehicle	An autonomous self-propelled vehicle, managed by a combination of video cameras, radar, accelerometers, a LIDAR system, and onboard software, which perform agricultural activities and transportation without the need for a driver. By eliminating the need to have someone at the wheel, this technology drastically reduces the time and cost of production and transportation. Agricultural vehicles operate in a significantly safer environment than conventional road systems. They could, therefore, see quicker adoption and serve as a steppingstone to fully autonomous self-driving vehicles across the board.
Bacteriophages	Majority of antibiotics in the world are used for sub-therapeutic applications in livestock operations, creating resistant superbugs incapable of treatment with our existing drugs. Bacteriophages may offer a non-antibiotic based way to combat common infections in livestock like mastitis. These microscopic organisms are a macromolecular bacterial virus that can be engineered to seek out and destroy specific strains of bacteria. Finding alternatives to antibiotics can help preserve the efficacy of these drugs for human uses while promoting livestock health and wellness.
Bee Vectoring Technologies	When it comes to U.S. crop production, honeybees are worth \$20 billion. These insects are essential to human survival, so there is increasing innovation in agriculture equipment to help protect bees and maximize their pollination capabilities. BVT uses commercially reared bees to deliver targeted crop controls through pollination, replacing chemical pesticides with an environmentally safe crop protection system. The system doesn't require spraying water or the use of tractors. Instead, the scientifically designed bumblebee hive allows bees to pick up a trace amount of pest control powders on their legs to spread as they travel within the field. This innovation in agriculture technology supports improved sustainable farming, crop yield, and soil quality. BVT's solution is suitable for many crops, including blueberries, sunflowers, apples, and tomatoes, and it also works for farms of all sizes.

Technology	Description
Big Data & Analytics	Big data and analytics techniques transform everyday farm data into actionable insights. Statistics of crop area, production, land use, irrigation, agricultural prices, weather forecasts, and crop diseases, lay the foundation for the next farming season. Analytical tools make use of data on weather events, farm equipment, water cycles, quality, and quantity of crops to extract information relevant to farm operations. This enables growers to identify patterns and relationships that may otherwise remain hidden. Several startups are offering solutions in farm analytics that enable farmers to take advantage of their field data. For example, analytical data fosters an understanding of the soil nutrient levels, acidity, and alkalinity as well as fertilizer requirements, enabling data-driven decision-making.
Bio-electricity Farm	Soil bacteria thriving around plants' root systems break down organic matter. Electrons transferred in the process can then be harvested for electricity using electrodes. Currently, the energy output is still low (around a watt per square meter), but the technology could either complement or compete with solar and wind in the future; especially considering how widely it could be deployed and the potential for installations to last decades.
Biofortification	The idea of breeding crops to increase their nutritional value as they grow. This can be done either through conventional selective breeding, or through genetic engineering. It's seen as an upcoming strategy for dealing with deficiencies of micronutrients in the developing world.
Bio-refinery	In nature, almost nothing goes to waste. Hence, a bio-refinery, instead of petrochemicals, transforms various types of biomass inputs into a wide assortment of bioproducts; with little to no waste. Combining the production of low-volume but high-value commodities (such as pharmaceuticals) along with large quantities of products such as biofuels, bioenergy, or food ingredients could improve overall efficiency and unit economics.
Blockchain	Blockchain technologies are used in agriculture to track plant information from the farms to the shelf. Powered by a decentralized database, this technology helps regulate the quality of food and its shelf life. The auditable database allows growers and marketers to monitor farm produce throughout the supply chain.
Cloud Computing	The future of farming is closely tied to cloud computing, and it has become so essential to agriculture that it is hard to imagine how the industry would function without it. Cloud computing allows agribusinesses to manage multiple technology solutions efficiently, vast amounts of data, predictive intelligence models, and other proprietary business intelligence tools under a single platform, helping to make important farming and business decisions. A specialized agriculture cloud platform can significantly reduce the time it takes for technology investments to pay off, lower barriers to innovation within the agriculture ecosystem, and bring together the capabilities needed to address major challenges. Many companies in the agriculture sector spend a lot of time and resources building fundamental technology infrastructure rather than focusing on innovation and intellectual property development in their specific areas of business. Just as railways were once a symbol of growth and prosperity, the agriculture cloud will become the central focus for new applications and developments by agritech companies, particularly as concerns about data security and privacy continue to dissipate.
Co-farming	Farmers have long shared or rented out equipment locally, but the tight timelines of a growing season make that hard because almost everyone in the same area needs the same equipment at the same time. The online sharing concept that has produced Airbnb and other examples of P2P services aimed at better utilizing existing capital is developing a farm machinery market. These P2P platforms let people look outside their local ecosystems, bringing more efficiency on agricultural productivity.

Technology	Description
Computer-Assisted Transgenesis	Genetic Engineering is aided by precision robotics with computer vision algorithms to streamline the production of transgenic organisms. This type of transgenesis will accelerate the study and the development of gene drive technology and the ability to modify organisms depending on the needs of the environment.
Connectivity Technologies	Smart farming is not possible without connectivity technologies like 5g, LPWAN, rural broadband, or satellite-enabled communication. 5G facilitates the adoption of IoT devices, robots, and sensors and enables them to communicate at high speeds. This enables farmers to monitor the data more accurately in real-time and take the required actions. High-speed internet using fiber optic cables aid the exchange of field data in real-time, which is crucial when it comes to improving accuracy. Connectivity technologies support other technologies like IoT, which ultimately work in coordination to form connected farms.
Context-Aware Biology Open Tool	Open tools and protocols that assist farmers with collecting data and distributed experimental conditions could help improve crop productivity and efficiency. Closed-loop pipetting technologies that can connect with wireless sample temperature sensors enables novel, real-time experimental feedback to the researcher or farmer. This can lead to fewer mistakes, better decision making, and increased overall scientific reproducibility.
Controlled Environment Agriculture	Fluctuating and extreme weather events constantly hamper conventional farming methods. Further, growing crops in populated cities, deserts, or other unfavorable conditions pose significant challenges. This is overcome by controlled environment agriculture (CEA). In CEA, plants are subjected to a controlled proportion of light, temperature, humidity, and nutrients. There are different growing environments, namely, indoor farming, vertical farming, and greenhouses, among others. There is an increased deployment of techniques like hydroponics and aeroponics which involve growing soilless plants in a liquid nutrient medium or steam. Another such technique is aquaponics, where plants and fish are cultivated simultaneously. Fish provides nutrients to plants while plants purify the water for the fish. CEA methods reduce pests and diseases, increase yield, and establish sustainable farming practices.
Crop Epigenetics	A manipulation mechanism of gene expressions in plants to improve crop yields and stress tolerance without making changes to the DNA sequence of a plant. The research and application of how and when genes are expressed in crops, under the influence of mostly external factors. Different from animals, plants are stationary and, consequently, more vulnerable to environmental stresses such as high temperature, drought, pathogens, parasites, and poor soil conditions. In general, those stressors tend to suppress the development and growth of plants, damaging their DNA.
Crop Sensors	Farmers may benefit from using crop sensors by effectively applying fertilizers and pesticides, especially the amount required. Variable rate technology is an excellent approach in this scenario. This technology allows you to feel the sensations of plants and then reduce the risk of leaching or runoff. The crops sensor calculates the number of resources needed for a particular crop and when to apply them.
Cyborg Sperm	A hybrid micromotor with microhelicis that is small enough to fit sperm cells helps guide the sperm's tail toward an egg. Guided by magnetic fields, the 'spermbot' does not harm the immune system or the reproductive cells. After fertilization, the robotic tail falls off. This technology has the potential to accelerate livestock and human reproduction, providing a better alternative to in-vitro fertilization especially when the cause of in-fertilization is related to motor problems on the sperm.

Technology	Description
Data Collection and Storage	The incorporation of big data into agriculture technology has enhanced the flow of information, facilitated more fast and precise analysis, and ultimately resulted in improved decision-making and strategic planning. Analyzing historical agricultural data, we may foresee potential outcomes, evaluate risks, and choose the best course of action to take. Thanks to improvements in agricultural technology, more and more information about farms can be collected and stored. Soil pH, relative humidity, nutrient levels, root and surface soil moisture values, vegetation productivity, crop types, field height, weather conditions, agricultural activities (irrigation, sowing, harvesting), and much more is available. It could be analyzing the field's volume and prior harvests, as well as make future harvest predictions, with the help of this agricultural data, which is presented on the platform in an accessible and simple format. In addition, this information has practical use in cooperative management, crop planning, and the identification of agricultural risks.
Decision Support System	Software and hardware systems that collect farmers' operational data can be extended to provide farmers with better insight into their fields. The data can support better decision making by providing recommendations about input applications, irrigation, and even which crops or varieties may provide the greatest yields. Some of these technologies can provide farmers with instructions about how to vary treatment of different areas of the same field as some stretches may require more inputs whereas some other may need less.
De-extinction	De-extinction, or resurrection biology, or species revivalism is the process of creating an organism, which is either a member of, or resembles an extinct species, or breeding population of such organisms. Cloning is the most widely proposed method, although selective breeding has also been considered. The technology might be necessary to maintain stable supply of food items such as bananas, chocolate and certain grape varieties that may be at risk because of a limited genetic pool and low diversity.
Digital Twins	A digital twin is a representation of a physical system that can help to understand, predict, and optimize performance. Data is collected from the physical asset, including information that cannot be observed, such as soil health. The digital twin analyses previous patterns to simulate future behavior, allowing farmers to act quickly if a deviation occurs. Digital twins are underpinned by remote operation, which is a hotly contested aspect to this so-called 'new phase of smart farming'. Supporters cite the capacity to conduct planning and control away from the site, and to carry out predictive analysis and real-time response, while critics highlight jobs lost due to automatization.
DNA Fingerprinting Food	The progress in biotech led to a dramatic drop in the cost of genome sequencing over the last three decades. This allows the strain, ancestry, and even origin of plant materials to be determined precisely at a reasonable price point. Marijuana, however controversial, is already the biggest cash crop in California and DNA fingerprinting could be either used as a forensic tool to ensure legal origin, or to enable a more personalized recommendation for the user. Consequently, a similar approach could be used for most other food products.

Technology	Description
Drones	Increasing farm productivity while saving costs is challenging. But drones, also known as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), help farmers overcome this hassle in an effective way. Drones collect raw data which translates into useful information for farm monitoring. Drones equipped with cameras facilitate aerial imaging and surveying of near and far-stretched fields. This data optimizes the application of fertilizers, water, seeds, and pesticides, driving precision agriculture. Moreover, drones facilitate livestock tracking, geofencing, and grazing monitoring. They fly over fields to capture images that range from simple visible-light photographs to multispectral imagery which helps in the crop, soil, and field analysis. Even though drones are not fit for poultry monitoring as their movement frightens birds, drones are effective for livestock monitoring, grazing monitoring, and crop cultivation. Startups are also working on drones capable of measuring the chlorophyll level, weed pressure, as well as soil mineral and chemical composition.
Endophytic Plant Protection	The deployment of fungal, bacterial, and microbial organisms naturally found in living plants to protect and improve crop performance. This is an eco-friendly approach than synthetic pesticides and fertilizers. The interface between plant roots and soil and their microbiota enhances plant mineral uptake, regulates chemical compounds, such as phytohormones that modulate plant growth and development, and protects plants from soil-derived pests and pathogens. They can produce a wide range of bioactive compounds with anticancer, cytotoxic, and insecticidal properties, making them attractive to the pharmaceutical and the skincare industry.
Farm Automation	Farm automation brings together agricultural machinery, computer systems, electronics, chemical sensors, and data management to improve equipment operation and decision-making, and ultimately, reduce human input and error. Reduced labor time, higher yields, and the efficient use of resources are driving the large-scale adoption of the technology. Farmers now use automated harvesters, drones, autonomous tractors, seeding, and weeding to transform how they cultivate their crops. The technology takes care of menial and recurring tasks, allowing them to focus on more critical functions. As with any field (no pun intended), automation can help employees save time, as the technology reduces the need for people to actively partake in a task.
Farm Management Software	Farm management software is an integrated platform that provides real-time data and information, like a digital checklist, to assist farmers with tracking daily activities. With this monitoring and reporting software, farmers can improve decision-making throughout all operations. An enterprise resource planning solution allows farms to streamline their processes and enables seamless collaborations. It lets users manage procurement, supply chain, finances, and processing from a single hub. This innovation in agriculture technology will continue to advance as internet-enabled devices become ubiquitous.
Farm Management System	The system monitors weather forecasts, tracks crop phases, estimates threat of plant diseases and analyses data from the farmer's electronic "field book". Thus, helping to make prognoses about fields, enabling users to keep track of costs and finally grow crops more efficiently.
Farm-in-a-Box	To farm in remote locations without access to a power grid or other conventional amenities, farmers will need complete solutions that cover all the basis. Farm-in-a-box products come complete with the hardware and software necessary to facilitate farming in off-grid locations. Some of these solutions may involve cargo containers, while others may provide capacities to support greenhouse grow operations, hydroponics, or indoor agriculture.

Technology	Description
Farm-to-Consumer Network	Consumers have recently shown an increased demand for products sourced from local farms or directly from agricultural producers. Technology may help consumers source food directly from farmers using mobile apps, online ordering, and wholesale platforms for chefs and restaurants. These platforms may help consumers access more nutritious, seasonal, and local produce.
Faster Flowering	Using the CRISPR gene-editing tool, researchers figured out how to make trees mature faster. They applied CRISPR to edit a flower repressor gene and drastically shortened the time it takes a poplar tree to flower—from 10 years down to just three months. It would typically take the plant a year to develop the systems to even produce flowers, and the team engineered the plant to mature in just a few days. The promise of this research is an accelerated time frame for tree breeding, as well as enhancement of trees' natural defenses against extreme heat, cold, and drought.
Floating Farm Barge	In regions challenged by poor access to land, low soil quality, or access to water, floating farms that rely on hydroponics, aquaculture, or other greenhouse growing methods may provide a new mechanism for cultivating food. Also, the mobile nature of a floating farm could assist with the logistical hurdles that have made it difficult to deliver fresh food to certain regions of the world. Solar panels could provide a source of power at sea.
Food Computer	A tabletop-sized, robotic-controlled environment that can help program plants to yield various phenotypic expressions. Even though most constructions are made from easily accessible components and expandable systems, the environmental variables which can be controlled are numerous, ranging from CO2 concentration to soil conductivity or root-zone temperature. This could lead to the adoption of standardized platforms for semi-automated, agricultural experiments, which can then be hacked, modified, shared, and upgraded over time.
Freight Drone	Applying pesticides today often involves using large quantities of each agent and spraying it over a vast area, impacting cost and health. A drone could be agile and accurate enough to apply just the right number of pesticides at a specific location. The agility of a drone could prove useful in mountainous farming regions, potentially opening new areas that are suitable for farming. They may also facilitate the combination of aerial seed planting and crop monitoring. Drone battery life and payload are limiting factors now.
Fruit Picking Robot	Traditional robots can only manipulate objects with a known geometry and location. Technology may eventually allow robots to determine the location of a piece of fruit, whether it is ready for picking, and how it should be gripped to prevent damage. Fundamental to this technology is creating a gripper that can achieve the delicate balance between gripping it securely and preventing damage. Vacuums may provide a viable solution.
Gene Drive	During reproduction, both of a gene's versions have a 50% chance of being inherited. Gene Drive increases the chance of a certain gene being passed to offspring, thereby minimizing the intervention needed for editing an entire population. This technology could be used to exterminate plagues and weeds. CRISPR genome editing is a potential avenue for enabling Gene Drive. There are, however, some limitations. Many generations are required for a gene to spread through an entire population. Also, the technology still needs considerable research before being practically applicable.

Technology	Description
Genome Editing (CRISPR)	Research into the biological, nutritional, and socioeconomic implications of CRISPR technology is starting to gain traction. CRISPR is a genetic engineering technique by which the genomes of living organisms are modified through deleting, adding, or altering sections of DNA. Advocates for CRISPR techniques claim that the use of this novel DNA leads to improved food safety (by knocking out antibiotic resistance to provide immunity against pathogens like salmonella), lengthened shelf life of perishable foods, development of new products that taste better and have other desirable traits for consumers. Other possible uses involve gene drives for pest extermination or in-vivo modifications to the genetic code.
Geographic Information Systems	Geographical information systems (GIS) are essential for the storage, analysis, and visualization of spatial data for precision agriculture needs. One of the most important ways that GIS-based agriculture technology is used in farming is to gather information about a region's crops, soil, climate, and topography by using satellites and drones. Furthermore, GIS in agriculture enables the use of GPS apps in conjunction with smart tools to optimize the spreading of fertilizer and pesticides.
Global Land Use Optimization	The amount of agricultural land is limited and unevenly distributed around the world, nonetheless, food self-reliance is crucial for national interests. This creates tension between a locally and globally optimal food supply system. Using modern scientific models and data it is possible to find optimal match between land and crops, creating world-wide agricultural commons. This could enable us to feed the expected 9 billion people in 2050 with far less land under cultivation, provided a global deal and reallocation were to take place.
GPS Technology	By using GPS data, precision agricultural technologies improve productivity while decreasing wasteful spending on inputs like seeds, fertilizer, pesticides, and fuel. In addition to providing location-based agricultural information, GPS can be used to facilitate communication between vehicles and streamline record-keeping when combined with farm management software. Among the many uses this technology enables in the agricultural sector are the following: monitoring and managing field operations, collecting, and analyzing data from the fields, accurate soil sampling, yield mapping, navigating and controlling of agricultural machinery, the ability to operate in low-visibility field conditions like heavy rain or fog.
Gustatory Hacking	The same way that eyesight can be tricked with visual illusions, taste can also be manipulated. 'Food hacking' can take various forms: changing perception of portion sizes or taste, tricking brain with VR or simply recreating products such as eggs or meat using more benign processes or ingredients. Still more of an art than mainstream science, gustatory hacking could be applied to issues ranging from overeating to reducing the environmental footprint of food production by helping consumers switch to better alternatives.
High-Albedo Crop	Modified plant species, with more reflective leaves, used to increase the albedo-effect to cool down temperatures in certain areas. Enhancing localized albedo (surface reflectivity) is a technique used in regional climate change adaptation in urban and agricultural settings. By increasing surface reflectivity of crops, solar radiation absorption is reduced, which in turn partially neutralizes the local warming effects of increased atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations while also conserving water resources and improving public health.

Technology	Description
High-speed 5G networks	The rollout of 5G technology is revolutionizing numerous industries by improving decision-making, production processes, and factory operations. Agriculture is also seeing significant benefits from this advanced technology due to its low latency, increased network capacity, and reliable high-speed data transfer. With 5G, transferring large amounts of data such as images, videos, 3D models, weather, and topographical information from connected farms can be quick and easy, saving time and improving AI/ML modeling accuracy. For example, data from the numerous cameras in a connected farm can be transferred with just one click, a task that previously took days using traditional networks. Overall, 5G will help accelerate agriculture's digitization for farmers and businesses.
Hydroponics	Hydroponics, a subset of hydroculture, is the method of growing plants without soil, using mineral nutrient solutions in a water solvent. Sundrop, for example, a company based in Australia, has developed a hydroponics seawater technology that combines solar, desalination, and agriculture to grow vegetables in any region. This system is sustainable, doesn't rely on fossil fuels (drawing its energy from the sun instead), and doesn't require land. Instead, its technologies integrate solar power, electricity generation, freshwater production, and hydroponics. The result: an equivalent quantity of food to that grown using traditional methods. By using hydroponics, Sundrop can put a seawater greenhouse—a combination of solar, desalination, and agriculture—to grow vegetables anywhere in the world. Plants grown with hydroponic methods don't need extensive root systems, allowing them to devote more energy to the production of leaves and fruit. They also reach maturity faster and are safe from pests and diseases due to their indoor cultivation.
Hyperspectral Imaging	Usefulness of hyperspectral imaging comes from the fact that different materials and processes often produce unique responses when subjected to various electromagnetic spectra. Applications have been numerous: surveillance (infrared cameras), food quality control (recognition of foreign material), or Earth imaging (Landsat satellites). The breakthroughs now, many of which come from Israel, promise miniaturization, and low costs, making it accessible to individuals and not only national agencies. Possible applications are endless, including checking fruit ripeness or composition, CO2/pollution concentration, and brain imaging--all of which may be coming to your cell phone soon.
Hypoallergenic Plant	Using genome editing technologies such as CRISPR/Cas9, it is possible to provide a cheap and easy way to modify the genes of any organism, including plants that contain allergens, as is the case for peanuts and wheat. Scientists have been tweaking the genes for the proteins linked to the causes of peanut allergies to create an allergy-free version of the snack.
In Silico Farming	A computational method that optimizes crop growth. It collects data from real crops in the field and creates a mathematical model to simulate how yields perform under any given circumstance. In silico studies are computer simulations with 3D models reflecting the real world as closely as possible. Unlike digital twins, in silico designs can react to specific inputs and provide conclusions for further analysis. In silico farming is a farming ecosystem transformed into code, where planting patterns, tillage systems, sunlight and shading, water availability, microbial interactions, and many other variables are digitally tested. By modeling the coupled plant-soil atmosphere management ecosystem, the simulated spatial resolution and precision output could potentially be comparable to a large number of physical sensors distributed in the field.

Technology	Description
Indoor Vertical Farming	Indoor vertical farming grows farm produce stacked above another in a closed and controlled environment. The technology uses growing shelves mounted vertically to increase crop yield in limited spaces. Quite often, the shelves don't require soil—they're either hydroponic (gardening practice that grows plants in water and nutrient solutions) or aeroponic (suspends the roots of the crops in the air, with emitters intermittently spraying them with water and nutrients). Indoor vertical farms enable growers to control variables such as light, temperature, water, and sometimes, carbon dioxide levels, allowing them to get healthier and bigger yields. Other benefits of the technology include 70% less water usage, which conserves energy, and reduced labor costs due to the use of robots for harvesting and planting. With regards to sustainability, the smaller footprint of vertical farms allows them to be placed closer to or even within areas of high population density, which reduces the need for transport and the harmful emissions associated with it. These facilities can also have a year-round growing cycle, which makes them more efficient and capable of delivering items that would otherwise be out of season regardless of the local climate.
Insects as Nutrients	Insects are very efficient animals. Compared with typical farm animals, they grow faster, have better conversion rate, require less space, and produce less greenhouse gases. An insect biorefinery takes this natural advantage further, upgrading biomass to high-quality protein that consumers can use in a variety of applications and co-producing range of industrial substrates, such as chitosan, lipids, and fertilizer materials.
Inspection Drone	Drones used for autonomous inspections in areas such as agriculture, aerial surveys, or traffic control. With reliable autonomy and collision avoidance, drones can take over tasks that are either too dangerous for humans to carry out or located in difficult-to-access areas, e.g., checking electric power lines, delivering medical supplies in emergency situations, or inspecting off-shore platforms and turbines.
Integration of the agri-ecosystem	The agriculture ecosystem is complex and includes a range of stakeholders, such as seed manufacturers, farming and food processing companies, technology providers, and governments. These stakeholders often operate independently of one another, which can limit innovation and collaboration. However, there is a trend towards agricultural digitization to address issues like food insecurity, climate risk, and supply chain disruptions. As a result, there will be increased collaboration between stakeholders in the value chain in 2023. Agritech companies will facilitate partnerships and information sharing and will be critical enablers within the agri-ecosystem. For example, virtual agronomists can be made available to millions of farmers around the world, allowing a single expert to monitor multiple farms. Additionally, purpose-built industry cloud platforms for agriculture may provide access to satellite imagery, data, and agri-intelligence, enabling experts to identify and address issues throughout the value chain quickly.
Internet of Things	The Internet of Things (IoT) is all the physical technological items that gather, process, and exchange information about data. It combines sensors, systems, and software that communicate over the Internet. In agriculture, IoT solutions help growers use their resources optimally to maximize crop yield, reduce water, pesticide, and fertilizer use, monitor soil moisture and other growing conditions, and reduce operational costs. Sensors help farmers monitoring their crops and livestock to ensure health and can even be used to suggest predictive maintenance for equipment. Sensors connected to greenhouses can record data on the best times for lighting, temperature, and humidity preferences of crops, and soil and water sensors can easily detect moisture and nitrogen levels, alerting farmers when crops require watering or fertilization. IoT solutions in agriculture have been improving and increasingly adopted recently.

Technology	Description
In-Vitro Meat	Animal protein grown in a lab as a substitute for human meat consumption. Deployment at scale has potential for massive, worldwide impact starting from reduction of CO2 emissions and soil degradation caused by certain methods of livestock production to stopping the spread of omni-antibiotic-resistant bacteria. The technology has been improving rapidly and costs have fallen by a factor of 5 in the last 2 years alone.
Laser Scarecrows	Pesky birds or rodents can be a menace to growing crops in an open field. In the past, farmers relied on traditional scarecrows to ward off hungry invaders. But today, farm owners and managers are turning to high-tech devices with motion sensors to keep birds from pillaging crops. After discovering that birds are sensitive to green, green laser light was developed. The light isn't visible by humans in sunlight, but it can shoot 600 feet across a field to startle birds before destroying crops. Early tests with laser scarecrows found that the devices can minimize crop damages by reducing the bird population around farmlands by up to 70% to 90%.
Livestock Farming Technology	Emerging livestock technologies provide farmers with data-driven insights, allowing them to streamline farm management, improve animal care, and boost productivity. Some of the many innovations redefining livestock farming are: 1) Automated dairy installations milk cows automatically without human intervention, and the milk sensors also help farmers monitor the milk quality, 2) Automated cleaning systems remove waste, enabling cleaner as disease-free environments, 3) Armenta's non-antibiotic treatment uses acoustic pulse technology (APT) for bovine mastitis, a cow disease responsible for over \$6 billion annual losses in the U.S. and Europe, 4) Automated feeder systems provide animals with feeding mixtures tailored to their specific needs and in the right amount, 5) Faromatics employs robotics, A.I., and big data to increase animal welfare and farm productivity.
Livestock Monitor	Managing animal health and identifying issues before they escalate is a crucial aspect of modern livestock operations. Wearable technologies and infrared cameras can already monitor animals' vital signs such as temperature, movement patterns, eating habits, and stress levels. The monitors can also send near real-time alerts to farmers, warning of events like the onset of labor or specimens becoming sick with diseases that can spread to other livestock.
LoRa Network	For a humidity sensor to talk to a sprinkler setup in the field, connectivity is a must; wireless communication being more of a prerequisite rather than extravagance. Yet, current communication protocols such as WiFi or Bluetooth have short ranges and high-power consumption whereas LoRa (Low power, high Range) has 2-15 kilometer range, and high energy efficiency. This solves the problems of having to replace batteries frequently and needing a lot of gateways (receivers) to cover a certain area.
Machine Learning and Data Analytics	Machines can collect data and interpret that data to help them learn and predict which traits and genes are best for crop production. This can help farmers all over the world know the best breed for their location and climate. Machine learning algorithms can also be used when selling products. The algorithms can show which products are the most popular and which are not selling well. This would help create successful forecasts for future farming.
Machine Vision	Machine vision is a technology that has been used in many industries and is now also beginning to be applied to agriculture. It is the process of using computer vision and image recognition to get information from images or videos. Machine vision can also be applied to a range of activities in agriculture, such as crop condition analysis, weed identification, harvesting. Machine vision can also be used to identify and automate the harvesting of crops such as apples and oranges. This can be done by mounting a camera on the harvesting equipment to detect when the fruit is ripe and ready to be harvested.

Technology	Description
Milkbot	Transponders attached to cows' necks use lasers to scan and map their underbellies. A computer charts each animal's "milking speed," giving each animal an individualized service. The algorithm also monitors the amount and quality of milk produced, the frequency of visits to the machine, how much each cow has eaten, and even the number of steps each cow has taken per day. This information improves the system and reduces the need to adjust their milking schedule to farmers' hours.
Miniature Mass Spectrometry	Allows rapid analysis of the chemical makeup of materials or physical objects. Miniature mass spectrometer would work using the same principles - vaporization, ionization, and spectral analysis of samples, but using only a fraction of the cost and size of current lab-confined devices. The main benefits of this technology include much faster field work (no more mailing the samples), but also detection of harmful chemicals and explosives in situ or possibly mundane uses, such as monitoring the ripening process of fruits.
Minichromosome Technology	Genetically modified food has taken some flak over recent years, with studies suggesting it may be linked to allergic reactions or include harmful toxins that can expose humans to health risks. Another issue is that G.M. food production can disrupt natural biodiversity or release toxins into the soil. Agricultural geneticists can apply minichromosome technology to enhance a plant's traits without altering the genes in any way. Since minichromosomes contain small amounts of genetic material, it's possible to use this technology to make plants more drought-tolerant or resistant to pests without interfering with the host's natural development. Minichromosome technology allows genetic engineers to create crops that require fewer pesticides, fungicides, and fertilizers, reducing reliance on harmful chemicals. It also lets them achieve bio-fortification and enhance a plant's nutritional content.
Modern greenhouses	In recent decades, the greenhouse industry has transformed from small facilities used primarily for research and aesthetic purposes (i.e., botanic gardens) to much larger facilities that compete directly with land-based conventional food production. Greenhouses are increasingly emerging that are large-scale, capital-infused, and urban-centered. As the market has grown dramatically, it has also experienced clear trends in recent years. Modern greenhouses are becoming increasingly tech-heavy, using LED lights and automated control systems to perfectly tailor the growing environment. Successful greenhouse companies are scaling significantly and locating their growing facilities near urban hubs to capitalize on the ever-increasing demand for local food. To accomplish these feats, the greenhouse industry is becoming increasingly capital-infused, using venture funding and other sources to build out the infrastructure to compete in the current market.
Morphic Water	The membranes that form when a water stream hits a smooth surface can be changed dynamically to create systems that can control the shape of a water membrane. This type of system could be applied to irrigation, making it easier to streamline water through a field or crop.
Mutagenesis	A method to induce genetic changes in DNA structure, affecting one or more genes, because of the interaction of certain environmental chemical compounds. It is an inexpensive and easy way to generate a high density of novel nucleotide diversity in the genomes of plants and animals, and as such is a research area that has been investigated for functional genomic studies as well as plant breeding. One of the most common chemicals used for mutagenesis in plants is ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS), which has already shown the ability to induce primarily single base point mutations.
Nitrogen Fixing Bacteria	Seeds can be coated with a bacterium that will later enable the plant to retrieve nitrogen from air. Before, this was only possible through a plant's roots in the soil. With this technology the need for environmentally damaging and expensive synthetic nitrogen-fertilization would be reduced.

Technology	Description
Open Phenome Library	Genetic makeup is basically fixed, but the way it manifests can change based on external conditions. A comprehensive database relating genetic information, environmental inputs and species-specific phenotypic outputs could help both scientists and growers to optimize production for very particular local conditions. Opening this type of data could facilitate knowledge dissemination or let farmers (not just major corporations) simulate and predict yields better.
Open-Source Agricultural Machinery	Much of the progress made in agriculture over the 20th century can be attributed to machinery and automation. Unfortunately, specialized equipment can be prohibitively expensive. Starting in 2011, a growing movement seeks to create and sharing (open source) designs of robust, inexpensive, easy-to-build machinery supporting more sustainable and self-sufficient lifestyles, particularly for farmers lacking a surplus of cash.
Optimized Photosynthesis	Plants use the enzyme Rubisco to convert carbon dioxide into sugar. However, this enzyme has limited efficiency and scientists have long considered it as something that can potentially be improved. Modifying Rubisco could boost the efficiency and yields of crops like rice and wheat. Similarly, increasing the carbon dioxide concentration would have the same effect. An enzyme found in algae could increase this concentration when built into crops. Development is still in the research phase. Also, due to the variances among local environments, it is unlikely that one single optimization will suffice.
Pollinating Robot Bee	A robot that replicates behavior from animals and insects can utilize existing movement patterns to perform a variety of functions. For example, a robot could mimic the process that an insect uses to pollinate flowers. Roughly one-third of all food and beverages are dependent on pollination, which is primarily performed by honeybees. Over the last decade, the honeybee's health has declined creating a temporary need for artificial pollinators.
Porous Nanozeolite	Microporous, crystalline solids with well-defined structures can be either natural or synthetic. Because of their structure, aluminosilicate variations, called zeolites, have been adopted by the industry as good adsorbents and catalysts. New configurations, and better productions methods, show great promise for environmental applications, such as water treatment or slow, steady release of fertilizers or moisture.
Precision Agriculture	Precision agriculture is an agricultural resource management strategy that collects, processes, and evaluates data and offers insights to help farmers optimize and increase soil quality and productivity. Management decisions count on precision agriculture data points to improve farmland and farm produce across several key areas (resource use efficiency, sustainability, profitability, productivity, quality). This innovation in agriculture technology uses big data to aid management decisions, enabling farmers to control crop yield variables like moisture level, soil condition, and microclimates to maximize output. It relies on remote sensing systems, drones, robotics, and automation to improve crop health and optimize agricultural resources, leading to more productivity.
Predictive Food Insecurity Warning System	Some food crises and emergencies can be foreseen. It might be due to significant likelihood of droughts or floods in certain regions, monocultures being susceptible to pests or structural issues, such as heavily reliance on a single staple food and a single import partner. The difference technology makes now is that near real-time data can be combined to create short- and mid-term warning signals of approaching food insecurity - ahead of time, like the earthquake or volcano warning systems.
Predictive Weather Models	Aggregating weather-based data from various locations can support the creation of predictive weather models that provide more accurate forecasting. More accurate weather forecasting can assist farmers with making numerous decisions like when to plant and when to harvest. It may also assist businesses that rely on commodity futures trading or other weather-based factors.

Technology	Description
Regenerative Agriculture	Regenerative agriculture describes farming and grazing practices that rebuild soil's organic matter and restore degraded soil biodiversity. There's a clear need for this technology-led practice: Decades of using chemicals, salt-based fertilizers, carbon mining, and harsh insecticides deplete the soil. Planting multiple types of crops together, rotating crops, cutting back on tilling, and reducing reliance on harsh chemicals can revitalize depleted soil, leading to improved yields, nutrient-rich crops, and improved resistance to flooding and drought. Further, regenerative farming facilitates fields to act as carbon sink through sequestration. This leads to fewer carbon emissions into the atmosphere and a lesser impact on climate change.
Restaurant Microculture	The food you eat often travels for weeks across thousands of miles before ending up on your table. The next batch of locally sourced food could come from controlled-environment agricultural units, the size of a shipping container, which can grow all sorts of food for small-scale cafeterias, restaurants, or bars. The self-contained farms will allow small scale producers to grow a variety of items on-site and offer some of the freshest food options possible.
RFID & Blockchain	Emerging technologies in agriculture include radio frequency identification (RFID) and blockchain. Farmers use RFID and blockchain to improve, track, and manage produce through their entire supply chain. Crops and animals alike are tagged with distinct ID numbers using RFID. Those ID numbers are then tracked using blockchain through the sales cycle, reducing waste, allowing customers to trace food to its source, and increasing supply chain visibility. Customers simply scan a barcode with their smartphone and see where their produce comes from, including details as specific as the type of soil it was grown in.
RNA Interference Spray	Instead of permanently modifying an organism's genome, it is now possible to block some specific genes using a spray-on for a temporary reversible effect. Rapidly dropping costs of biotech and research efforts have made it possible to delay ripening and withering, to kill pests selectively, or to temporarily increase the drought-resistance of crops. Although still experimental, the technology is even more appealing compared to standard GMOs because it could be made species-specific, non-toxic to humans, and biodegradable.
Robot Farm	Manned entirely by programmed machines and operated completely by sensors, these 'plant factories' sow seeds, water plants, and care for crops in an automated fashion. The controlled environments can rely on natural or LED lighting and eliminate the use of pesticides and herbicides that are often necessary in open fields. This type of factory can increase production and efficiency, reduce waste, and lower labor costs.
Robotic Farm Labor	Most robots used in agriculture are designed to replace human labor at the harvesting stage, e.g. fruit-picking robots, driverless tractors, or milkbots. So far, proper execution of new tasks has been difficult because of specificity and peculiarities of trade (e.g., the size and color of the fruit to be picked). However, progress in AI may eventually facilitate the creation of self-learning robots that can take over other horticultural tasks such as pruning, weeding, spraying, and monitoring.
Robotic Technology	Robotic farm labor technology appears to be a viable choice for precision agricultural needs because it can do monotonous tasks without sacrificing accuracy. The autonomous performance of such robots would allow for continuous field management and improved agricultural productivity and efficiency because of the robot's ability to gather information about its environment on its own. Autonomous devices operated remotely via telemetry are currently the most well-known and successful agricultural robotic technology.

Technology	Description
Robot-Monitored Agriculture System	Tiny sensors (accelerometers, gyros, magnetometers, and often pressure sensors), small GPS modules, incredibly powerful processors, and a range of digital radios have the potential to be used in agriculture for actions that once relied on eyesight. Sensor-controlled monitoring for stats such as nutrients, water-stress, disease, insect infestations, and overall plant health in aeroponic and hydroponic plantations will be able to increase success in agricultural operations.
Satellite Remote Sensing Technology	The use of satellites has revolutionized field monitoring by greatly increasing both the sheer volume of agricultural data and the frequency with which it is collected. Satellite sensors monitor, measure, and record the electromagnetic radiation reflected or emitted by Earth and its environs for further analysis and data extraction. With agriculture satellite technology, such as current and historical satellite images, you can track crop growth throughout the season even in vast, inaccessible areas. This information is beneficial for various purposes, including assessing the effectiveness of agricultural practices.
Seaweed Forest	Covering as little as 9% of ocean's surface with algal forests could not only provide enough fuel to substitute the entirety of fossil fuel consumption, but also remove carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and supply food at the same time. Moreover, this oceanic afforestation may help fisheries recover and increase the diversity of marine life.
Self-organizing Robots	Algorithms that enable collective artificial intelligence could facilitate teamwork between autonomous robots. This would make it possible for robots to perform complex operations subject to real world dynamics such as physical interactions and variability. By letting the software run alone, this self-organizing robot could solve problems caused by their environment without the need of human intervention. This type of robot could have applications in many aspects of the food production chain, from food factories to farms, taking care of the whole food system.
Self-Supplied Renewable Energy	Solar, wind, geothermal, and biomass energy could be self-supplied by farmers, powering a variety of farming tools including irrigation, grain drying, heat for livestock barns and greenhouses, and machinery. Tapping into renewable energy promotes food security by providing an alternative power source that does not rely on fossil fuels, which have been tied to environmental decline. Besides, energy self-supply reduces costs on the long-term, reduces production uncertainty, and increases farmer autonomy.,
Smart Agriculture Sensors	Weather conditions, plant moisture, soil temperature and fertility, pest infestations, and weed locations can all be determined with the help of agriculture sensor technology. The use of this data assists growers, agri-consultants, insurers, and others involved in the agricultural sector in making more informed decisions, leading to more output from farms at lower costs.
Sperm Transplantation	To transfer spermatogonia stem cells from the testis of a donor male animal to a recipient male, which could result in the recipient continuously producing the donor's sperm. This technique would make it possible to develop a perpetual semen supply with certain desired traits like fitness for milk production, beef production, or survivability while also ensuring that they are maintained through reproductive cycles
Super Water Absorbing Material	With a surface area of 800 square meters per gram of material, Upsalite is an extremely porous magnesium carbonate. This enables it to absorb big quantities of liquid to for example create a dry environment or to clean up an oil spill. In agriculture, it could improve food storage by extracting water from the harvested crops.
Synthetic Apiary	Creating a controlled environment within urban settings can help establish, preserve, and support bee colonies, which are one of the most important species on the planet. Within the apiary, the controlled atmosphere and sensing technologies can track behavioral paradigms and hive health metrics.

Technology	Description
Terraforming Desert	Although most arable land is already under cultivation, deserts are still largely devoid of human activity. Combining inexpensive solar power for desalination and modern horticulture and agriculture could transform hot, dry, and arid land into either more livable habitats or new farmland. Pilot projects are already underway in Jordan. The falling cost of solar power and the growing pressure on food and energy supplies will likely generate new interest in similar projects.
Transgenic Organism	An organism that incorporates genetic material from different species. Originally used for production of useful pharmaceutical compounds (pharming) using bacteria and viruses, the technology now enables the production of glow-in-the-dark cats, or DIY glowing bacteria. It also opens endless opportunities for the transfer of traits between species.
Underwater Farm	Underwater pods designed to cultivate seaweed and other marine species by taking advantage of all the characteristics found in seawater, such as constant temperature and protection from exposure to land-based extreme weather conditions. Farming aquatic flora and fauna offshore in the open ocean could be a more sustainable approach to feed a growing world population with low environmental impacts. Different from underground hydroponic pods that depend on cooling and heating systems to regulate the temperature, underwater farms offer a more stable environment to yield crops. Underwater pods are usually submerged five to eight meters below the surface, providing a steady temperature to culture, while avoiding exposure to land-based extreme weather conditions.
Upgrading Photosynthesis	Genetically modifying crops with upgrades could dramatically increase yields without needing to increase the other resources required for cultivation. Photosynthesis is the biological process green plants and some organisms use to harness sunlight to produce energy out of CO ₂ and water, and researchers are working on several projects to upgrade it. Simply over-exposing plants to sunlight doesn't have the same effect—more light can damage cells unless they turn on a biological system called quenching that's capable of flushing out the excess energy. On cloudy days, plants turn off quenching so they can hold on to the excess energy. This process of turning quenching on and off takes time, can be unpredictable, and creates enormous inefficiencies. Scientists hope that with genetic engineering, they can speed up the quenching process. In 2022, modified soybean plants were shown to yield 20% more thanks to a supercharged photosynthesis system. Researchers are also working on cowpeas and rice.
Vertical Farm	Vertical farms that use blue and red LED lighting to grow organic, pesticide-free food inside highly optimized and automated indoor environments. They use less water, less energy, and enable growing food either underground or year-round regardless of climate.
Water Management Software	Irrigation is a vital method of providing water to drylands that usually have insufficient rainfall to make them arable. However, while this is a crucial aspect of farming today, many farmers still irrigate their fields with wasteful amounts of water. Besides wasting over two-thirds of the water, flood irrigation can overwater plants, affecting their growth. It could also carry excess fertilizers into streams and lakes, contaminating freshwater sources. Innovation and technology in agriculture offer farmers more sustainable ways to provide sufficient water to plants. For instance, N-Drip, a micro drip irrigation system, allows water to slowly drip to plants' roots, creating the right environment for crops to thrive. The technology reduces water usage by up to 50% and improves crop quality.

7.2. Table A2. Search Dates for Studies on the SJOS Impact of Emerging Technologies

	Decision Tools (Cluster 1)	Gene Change (Cluster 2)	Integrative technology (Cluster 3)	Robot Farmers (Cluster 4)	Rural-Urban (Cluster 5)	Transparent Food (Cluster 6)
Biodiversity	19.01.2024	29.01.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Climate change	19.01.2024	30.01.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Nutrient flow	19.01.2024	30.01.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Land use	20.01.2024	31.01.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Water use	20.01.2024	31.01.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Chemical Pollution	21.01.2024	31.01.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Aerosol loading	22.01.2024	31.01.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Nutritional Security	23.01.2024	01.02.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Health	23.01.2024	01.02.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Social equity	23.01.2024	01.02.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024
Economy	26.01.2024	02.02.2024	05.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024	06.02.2024

7.3. Table A3. Keywords and General Structure of Search Queries Used for Literature Search on Web of Science

Basic structure of WoS search query	"Decision category keyword(s)" and agricultur* and dimension keyword(s) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
Decision categories	<p>Decision tools</p> <p>Context aware biology open tool, decision support system, In-silico farming, predictive weather model, Artificial intelligence, digital twins, machine vision, big data and analytics, blockchain, cloud competing</p> <p>Y = ("context-aware biology open tool")</p> <p>Y = ("in-silico farm*")</p> <p>Y = ("predictive weather model*")</p> <p>Y = ("artificial intelligence" or AI)</p> <p>Y = ("decision support system")</p> <p>Y = ("digital twins")</p> <p>Y = ("big data")</p> <p>Y = ("blockchain")</p> <p>Y = ("cloud competing")</p>
	<p>Gene change</p> <p>algae-based meal replacement, bacteriophages, biofortification, computer-assisted transgenesis, cyborg sperm, de-extinction, endophytic plant protection, gene drive, genome editing, in-vitro meat, nitrogen fixing bacteria, optimized photosynthesis, porous nanozeolite, RNA interference spray, Mini chromosome technology, upgrading photosynthesis, transgenic organism,</p> <p>Y = ("algae-based meal replacement")</p> <p>Y = ("bacteriophages*")</p> <p>Y = ("biofortification")</p> <p>Y = ("computer-assisted transgenesis")</p> <p>Y = ("cyborg sperm")</p> <p>Y = ("de-extinction")</p> <p>Y = ("endophytic plant protection*")</p> <p>Y = ("gene drive")</p> <p>Y = ("genome editing")</p> <p>Y = ("in-vitro meat")</p> <p>Y = ("nitrogen fixing bacteria*")</p>

Integrative technology	<p>Y = ("porous nanozeolite") Y = ("RNA interference spray*") Y = ("mini chromosome technology*") Y = ("upgrading photosynthesis*") Y = ("transgenic organism*") agricultural linguistic model, co-farming, farm-to-consumer network, open phenome library, predictive food insecurity warning system, carbon farming, RFID and blockchain Y = ("agricultural linguistic model*") Y = ("co-farming") Y = ("farm-to-consumer network*") Y = ("open phenome library*") Y = ("predictive food insecurity warning system*") Y = ("regenerative agriculture") Y = ("RFID and blockchain")</p>
Robot farmers	<p>animal-robot interaction, atmospheric water harvesting, autonomous agriculture vehicle, bio-electricity farm, pollinating robot bee, bio-refinery, freight drone, laser scarecrows, milk Bot, robot farm, robotic farm labor, robot-monitored system, farm automation, Y = ("animal-robot interaction") Y = ("atmospheric water harvesting*") Y = ("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") Y = ("bio-electricity farm*") Y = ("bio-refinery") Y = ("freight drone") Y = ("laser scarecrows*") Y = ("milk Bot") Y = ("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") Y = ("robotic farm labor") Y = ("farm automation")</p>
Rural urban	<p>3D printed food, automated home farming, farm-in-a-box, floating farm barge, seaweed forest, super water absorbing material, vertical farm,</p>

<p>Transparent food</p>	<p>Y = ("3D printed food") Y = ("automated home farming*") Y = ("farm-in-a-box") Y = ("floating farm barge") Y = ("seaweed forest") Y = ("super water absorbing material*") Y = ("vertical farm") agro-waste biodegradable coating, augmented reality information transfer, DNA fingerprinting food, food computer, hyperspectral imaging, miniature mass spectrometry, food nano tagging, Y = ("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") Y = ("augmented reality information transfer*") Y = ("DNA fingerprinting food") Y = ("food computer") Y = ("hyperspectral imaging") Y = ("miniature mass spectrometry") Y = ("food nanotagging*")</p>
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DECISION TOOLS TECHNOLOGY

<p>Biodiversity</p>	<p>Biodiversity, "genetic diversity", "functional diversity", "biosphere integrity", (extinction NEAR/2 rate), (species NEAR/2 variability) Y and agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories) (TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy) (TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
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	<p>(TS=("predictive weather model*")AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=(" digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Climate change	<p>"climate change", "greenhouse gas*", "global warming"</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming")))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming")))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("predictive weather model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data ") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Nutrient flow	<p>((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive weather model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Land use	<p>"forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conversion) or deforestation or "land use change"</p> <p>Y and agricultur*and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive weather model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("big data") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=(" blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Water use	<p>((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)) (Topic and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive weather model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
Chemical pollution	<p>"chemical pollut*", "novel entities", chlorofluorocarbon, pesticide, "heavy metal", microplastics</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive weather model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Aerosol loading	air, air pollution, "air pollut*", "particulate matter", sulfate, nitrate or carbon emission

Y and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

(TS=(" context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("predictive weather model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("big data") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
Nutritional security	<p>food, undernourishment, hunger</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive weather model") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Health	health

	<p>Y and agricultur* and health (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive weather model") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Social equity	<p>social equity</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and social equity (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive weather model") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Economy	<p>income or (income NEAR work)</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive weather model") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Resilience	<p>resilien*</p> <p>Y and resilien* (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("context-aware biology open tool") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-silico farm*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=(" predictive weather model") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("artificial intelligence") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("decision support system") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("digital twins") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("big data*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("blockchain") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cloud competing") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
GENE CHANGE	
Biodiversity	Biodiversity, "genetic diversity", "functional diversity", "biosphere integrity", (extinction NEAR/2 rate), (species NEAR/2 variability)

Y and agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(" genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	<p>(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("mini chromosome technology*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("transgenic organism*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Climate change	<p>"climate change", "greenhouse gas*", "global warming"</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("mini chromosome technology*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	<p>(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("transgenic organism*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Nutrient flow	<p>((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("mini chromosome technology*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("transgenic organism*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Land use	<p>"forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conversion) or deforestation or "land use change"</p> <p>Y and agricultur*and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("mini chromosome technology*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("transgenic organism*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

Water use

((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))

Y and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)) (Topic and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories))

(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
	(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
	(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
	(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
	(TS=("mini chromosome technology*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
	(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
	(TS=("transgenic organism*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
Chemical pollution	"chemical pollut*", "novel entities", chlorofluorocarbon, pesticide, "heavy metal", microplastics
	Y and agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
	(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	<p>(TS=("mini chromosome technology*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("transgenic organism*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Aerosol loading	<p>air, air pollution, "air pollut*", "particulate matter", sulfate, nitrate or carbon emission</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("mini chromosome technology*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("transgenic organism*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

Nutritional security food, undernourishment, hunger

Y and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	<p>(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("mini chromosome technology*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("transgenic organism") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Health	<p>health</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and health (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("transgenic organism") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Social equity	<p>social equity</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and social equity (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("transgenic organism") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

Economy

income or (income NEAR work)

Y and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	<p>(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("transgenic organism") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Resilience	<p>resilien*</p> <p>Y and resilien* (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("algae-based meal replacement") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bacteriophages*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("biofortification") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("computer-assisted transgenesis") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("cyborg sperm") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("de-extinction") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("endophytic plant protection*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("gene drive") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("genome editing") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("in-vitro meat") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("nitrogen fixing bacteria*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("porous nanozeolite") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RNA interference spray*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("upgrading photosynthesis*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("transgenic organism") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
INTEGRATIVE TECHNOLOGY	
Biodiversity	<p>Biodiversity, "genetic diversity", "functional diversity", "biosphere integrity", (extinction NEAR/2 rate), (species NEAR/2 variability) Y and agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
Climate change	<p>"climate change", "greenhouse gas*", "global warming"</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Nutrient flow	<p>((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Land use	<p>"forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conversion) or deforestation or "land use change"</p> <p>Y and agricultur*and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
Water use	<p>((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Chemical pollution	<p>"chemical pollut*", "novel entities", chlorofluorocarbon, pesticide, "heavy metal", microplastics</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Aerosol loading	<p>air, air pollution, "air pollut*", "particulate matter", sulfate, nitrate or carbon emission</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Nutritional security	<p>food, undernourishment, hunger</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Health	<p>health</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and health (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Social equity	<p>social equity</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and social equity (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Economy	<p>income or (income NEAR work)</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Resilience	<p>resilien*</p> <p>Y and resilien* (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agricultural linguistic model*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("co-farming") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-to-consumer network*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("open phenome library*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("predictive food insecurity warning system*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("regenerative agriculture") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("RFID and blockchain") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
ROBOT FARMERS TECHNOLOGY	
Biodiversity	<p>Biodiversity, "genetic diversity", "functional diversity", "biosphere integrity", (extinction NEAR/2 rate), (species NEAR/2 variability)</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

Climate change	<p>"climate change", "greenhouse gas*", "global warming"</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
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Nutrient flow	<p>((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("milk Bolt") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
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Land use	<p>"forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conversion) or deforestation or "land use change"</p> <p>Y and agricultur*and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
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Water use

((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))
Y and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)) (Topic
and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)
(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR
(withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*")
NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*")
NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR
(withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or
extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or
extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw*
or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or
extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface
water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw*
or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw*
or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

Chemical pollution “chemical pollut*”, “novel entities”, chlorofluorocarbon, pesticide, “heavy metal”, microplastics

Y and agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”)
(Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

(TS=(“animal-robot interaction”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“atmospheric water harvesting*”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“autonomous agriculture vehicle*”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“bio-electricity farm*”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“bio-refinery”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“freight drone”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“laser scarecrows*”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“milk Bot”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“robot farm*” or “robot-monitored system”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“robotic farm labor”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=(“farm automation”) AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or “heavy metal”))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

Aerosol loading	<p>air, air pollution, "air pollut*", "particulate matter", sulfate, nitrate or carbon emission</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
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	<p>(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Food	<p>food, undernourishment, hunger</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Health	<p>Health</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and health (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Social equity	<p>social equity</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and social equity (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Economy	<p>income or (income NEAR work)</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Resilience	<p>resilien*</p> <p>Y and resilien* (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("animal-robot interaction") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("atmospheric water harvesting*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("autonomous agriculture vehicle*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-electricity farm*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("bio-refinery") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("freight drone") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("laser scarecrows*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("milk Bot") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robot farm*" or "robot-monitored system") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("robotic farm labor") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm automation") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
TRANSPARENT FOOD TECHNOLOGY	
Biodiversity	<p>Biodiversity, "genetic diversity", "functional diversity", "biosphere integrity", (extinction NEAR/2 rate), (species NEAR/2 variability)</p>

	<p>Y and agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Climate change	<p>"climate change", "greenhouse gas*", "global warming"</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p>

	<p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Nutrient flow	<p>((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Land use	<p>"forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conversion) or deforestation or "land use change"</p> <p>Y and agricultur*and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Water use	<p>((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))</p>

Y and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

Chemical pollution "chemical pollut*", "novel entities", chlorofluorocarbon, pesticide, "heavy metal", microplastics

Y and agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	<p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Aerosol loading	<p>air, air pollution, "air pollut*", "particulate matter", sulfate, nitrate or carbon emission</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

Nutritional security food, undernourishment, hunger

Y and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)

(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)

	(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
Health	<p>health</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and health (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Social equity	<p>social equity</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and social equity (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Economy	<p>income or (income NEAR work)</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)
Resilience	<p>resilien*</p> <p>Y and resilien* (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("agro-waste biodegradable coating*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("augmented reality information transfer*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("DNA fingerprinting food") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food computer") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("hyperspectral imaging") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("miniature mass spectrometry") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("food nanotagging*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
RURAL URBAN TECHNOLOGY	
Biodiversity	<p>Biodiversity, "genetic diversity", "functional diversity", "biosphere integrity", (extinction NEAR/2 rate), (species NEAR/2 variability)</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and (biodiversity or "genetic diversity" or "functional diversity" or "biosphere integrity" or (extinction NEAR/2 rate) or (species NEAR/2 variability)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Climate change	<p>"climate change", "greenhouse gas*", "global warming"</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("climate change" or "greenhouse gas*" or "global warming"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Nutrient flow	<p>((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((usage or use or appl*) NEAR/2 (nitrogen or phosph* or fertilizer)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Land use	<p>"forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conversion) or deforestation or "land use change"</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p>

	<p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("forest cover" or (land NEAR/2 conver*) or deforestation or "land use change")) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Water use	<p>((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use))</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ((groundwater or freshwater or "blue water" or "surface water*") NEAR (withdraw* or extract* or use)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Chemical pollution	<p>"chemical pollut*", "novel entities", chlorofluorocarbon, pesticide, "heavy metal", microplastics</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal") (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and ("chemical pollut*" or "novel entities" or chlorofluorocarbon or pesticide or microplastic* or "heavy metal"))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Aerosol loading	<p>air, air pollution, "air pollut*", "particulate matter", sulfate, nitrate or carbon emission</p>

	<p>Y and agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and (aerosol or (air NEAR/4 pollut*) or (fuel NEAR/2 combustion) or (partic* NEAR/2 (pollution or matter)) or ((sulf* or nitrate or carbon) NEAR/4 emission)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Nutritional security	food, undernourishment, hunger

	<p>Y and agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and (food or undernourish* or hung*))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Health	<p>health</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and health (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

	<p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and health)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Social equity	<p>social equity</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and social equity (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and social equity)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Economy	<p>income or (income NEAR work)</p> <p>Y and agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)) (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p>

	<p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(agricultur* and (income or (income NEAR work)))) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>
Resilience	<p>resilien*</p> <p>Y and resilien* (Topic) and Agriculture, Multidisciplinary or Agricultural Economics & Policy (Web of Science Categories)</p> <p>(TS=("3D printed food") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("automated home farming*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("farm-in-a-box") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("floating farm barge") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("seaweed forest") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("super water absorbing material*") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p> <p>(TS=("vertical farm") AND TS=(resilien*)) AND WC=(Agriculture, Multidisciplinary OR Agricultural Economics & Policy)</p>

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